

Phenoxytacrine Derivatives: Low-Toxicity Neuroprotectants Exerting Affinity to Ifenprodil-Binding Site and Cholinesterase Inhibition

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Abstract

Tacrine (THA), a long withdrawn drug, is still a popular scaffold used in medicinal chemistry, mainly for its good reactivity and multi-targeted effect. However, THA-associated hepatotoxicity is still an issue and must be considered in drug discovery based on the THA scaffold. Following our previously identified hit compound 7-phenoxytacrine (7-PhO-THA), we systematically explored the chemical space with 30 novel derivatives, with a focus on low hepatotoxicity, anticholinesterase action, and antagonism at the

GluN1/GluN2B subtype of the NMDA receptor. Applying the down-selection process based on *in vitro* and *in vivo* pharmacokinetic data, two candidates, **I-52** and **II-52**, selective GluN1/GluN2B inhibitors thanks to the interaction with the ifenprodil-binding site, have entered *in vivo* pharmacodynamic studies. Finally, compound **I-52**, showing only minor affinity to AChE, was identified as a lead candidate with favorable behavioral and neuroprotective effects using open-field and prepulse inhibition tests, along with scopolamine-based behavioral and NMDA-induced hippocampal lesion models. Our data show that compound **I-52** exhibits low toxicity often associated with NMDA receptor ligands, and low hepatotoxicity, often related to THA-based compounds.

Keywords

Alzheimer's disease; electrophysiology; glutamate receptor; acetylcholinesterase; neuroprotection; *in vivo*; Tacrine

Introduction

Tacrine (THA; 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-9-aminoacridine) was the first FDA-approved drug for treatment of Alzheimer's disease (AD), indirectly stimulating the cholinergic system by the inhibition of acetylcholinesterase (AChE; E.C. 3.1.1.7). However, the mechanism seems to be more complex and involves interaction with other targets and receptors [1, 2]. THA was later withdrawn from clinical use due to hepatotoxicity [3, 4].

Tacrine is a popular scaffold used in medicinal chemistry, mainly because of its excellent reactivity and multi-targeted effect. This has led to a plethora of THA-based hybrids (for reviews, see [5-8]), although the so-called multi-target directed (MTDL) approach itself suffers from many limitations [9]. Nevertheless, the neuroprotective effect of THA and its interaction with NMDA receptors is well documented [10], as is also so for several of its derivatives *in vivo* [11-15].

However, THA-associated toxicity, especially hepatotoxicity, is still an issue and must be taken into consideration in drug discovery based on the THA scaffold. We have recently shown that 7-phenoxytacrine (7-PhO-THA) is a CNS-permeable dual AChE and NMDA receptor (NMDAR) inhibitor that potently inhibits GluN1/GluN2B receptors via an ifenprodil-binding site, in addition to its voltage-dependent inhibitory effect at both GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors. Furthermore, 7-PhO-THA exerts neuroprotective efficacy *in vivo* with no behavioral side effects typical for NMDA receptor antagonists [16]. In addition, we have recently shown that owing to its 7-phenoxy substituent, 7-PhO-THA can bypass the biotransformation pathway of THA through 7-OH-THA to quinone methide [17, 18], which is considered a culprit for hepatotoxicity [19]. It should be noted however that a simple substitution in position 7 does not guarantee the avoidance of formation of 7-OH-THA, as could be illustrated by 7-methoxytacrine (7-MEOTA), which was designed to avoid such liver biotransformation [20], but in which the opposite is true, with 7-MEOTA metabolically generating 7-OH-THA similarly to THA [17].

An extensive list of known NMDAR modulators acts by competitive, allosteric, or open-channel blocking mechanisms. Following the recent success with esketamine, a worldwide boom in the development of

modulators of NMDARs is evident in academia and industry. In particular, the GluN2B-NMDAR attracts attention, as selective antagonists have shown effectiveness against neurodegenerative diseases such as AD and Parkinson's disease, as well as epilepsy, pain, and depression [21, 22]. In addition, the model of the GluN2B-NMDAR antagonist, ifenprodil, has been known for a long time as a neuroprotective compound against ischemic injury induced pathology [23]. Additionally, recent studies with ifenprodil confirmed its capability to rescue synapses, improve neurocognitive functions [24], or, in general, protect against excitotoxicity [25].

Thus, the aim of our study was to explore the chemical space around the hit compound 7-PhO-THA, emphasizing the neuroprotective efficacy of the novel derivatives in parallel with low hepatotoxic premises, by preparation of a series of 30 derivatives and investigation of the biological properties stemming from their dual action, with emphasis on antagonism on the GluN2B-NMDAR. After assessing *in vitro* activity for all 30 compounds within the series, we applied a down-selection process, where the most promising compounds (**I-52** and **II-52**) were minutely inspected in a battery of behavioral and neuroprotective experiments using various models *in vivo*.

Results and Discussion

Chemistry

All the newly designed target compounds were synthesized as shown in **Scheme 1**. Compounds **I-III 50-60** were prepared in a four-step chemical synthesis according to the previously described method [26, 27]. The initial step involved the nucleophilic substitution of **1-6** by compound **7** in the presence of CuBr, Cs₂CO₃, and L1, followed by hydrolysis of **8-13** with MeOH/H₂O and KOH. Cyclo-condensation of the different substituted 4-phenoxyanilines **14-24** with esters **25-27** afforded the intermediates **I-III 28-38**. These were chlorinated using POCl₃ to obtain compounds **I-III 39-49**. Finally, a primary amino group was introduced by nucleophilic substitution by ammonia in phenol. The resulting base compounds **I-III 50-60** were treated with a 1 M solution of HCl in MeOH to give the hydrochloride salts in good overall yields (7-65%).

Scheme 1. General procedure for the synthesis of 7-PhO-THA derivatives (compounds I-III 50-60) *i*) 5-10 mol% CuBr; Cs₂CO₃ (2.0 eq.); L1 = 1-(2-pyridinyl)acetone (0.2 eq.); DMSO; 24 h; 90 °C; *ii*) MeOH/H₂O (2:1); KOH (7.5 eq.); Microwave 90 min; 160 °C; *iii*) PTSA (0.01 eq.); toluene; 24 h; 150 °C; *iv*) diphenyl ether; 20 min; 220-240 °C; heptane; *v*) POCl₃ (7.8 eq.); 1 h; 130 °C; *vi*) NH₃ (g); phenol (10.0 eq.); 2 h; 180 °C; *vii*) MeOH; HCl (25% in H₂O), RT

The cytotoxicity and inhibitory activity of 7-PhO-THA derivatives at cholinesterases and NMDARs

First of all, when assessing cytotoxicity as a predictor of *in vivo* toxicity, it is important to consider also the compound's lipophilicity, reflecting its water solubility. The results show that the majority of the tested compounds fall within the range defined by the parent compounds (as detailed in **Table 1**).

Notably, THA exhibited the lowest cytotoxicity, whereas by contrast, 7-PhO-THA emerged as one of the most cytotoxic compounds. Such finding was confirmed by us even in human primary hepatocytes, despite the fact that such cytotoxicity is very likely not associated with the formation of quinone-methide [17].

Furthermore, we have evaluated the dual potential of our newly synthesized compounds, since 7-PhO-THA has been demonstrated as a dually-acting compound capable of inhibiting both AChE and NMDARs to a similar extent [16]. Indeed, all the compounds in our study exhibited the ability to inhibit both cholinesterases, with their IC_{50} values falling within the range of units to tens of μM (**Table 1**). The only exception was compound **I-51**, which showed ineffectiveness against hBChE. Notably, compound **III-60** displayed submicromolar efficacy against AChE while **II-52** showed submicromolar efficacy against both hAChE and hBChE, highlighting it as a promising dual-activity candidate. Additionally, compounds **I-56** and **III-58** proved to be hAChE and hBChE selective, respectively.

We then focused on the inhibitory action of the newly synthesized compounds at the NMDARs. Given the predicted effect of the new derivatives towards the GluN1/GluN2B subtype of NMDAR, we first performed electrophysiological measurements on HEK293 cells expressing the wild-type (WT) version of human GluN1/GluN2B (hGluN1/hGluN2B) receptors. Since *i*) our previous study showed that 7-PhO-THA selectively acts on GluN1/GluN2B receptors in a voltage-independent manner with an IC_{50} value of $\sim 2 \mu\text{M}$ [16], and *ii*) we wanted to test a large number of novel derivatives (30 in total); we first measured the relative degree of inhibition of each compound at a concentration of $1 \mu\text{M}$ on L-glutamate-induced currents. These measurements were performed under steady-state conditions at a membrane potential of -60 mV . Our experiments showed that all of the studied compounds exhibited an inhibitory effect, ranging from 6.7% (compound **I-58**) to 57.6% (compound **III-52**), under the given conditions (**Table 1**).

Next, based on *in vitro* and pharmacokinetic properties (see below), we selected two derivatives for detailed electrophysiological analysis: namely, compound **II-52** (which demonstrated about 26% of relative inhibition at the $1 \mu\text{M}$ concentration) and compound **I-52** (which demonstrated about 35% inhibition at the $1 \mu\text{M}$ concentration); see **Table 1**. In our previous study we also observed the non-voltage-dependent inhibitory effect of 7-PhO-THA on GluN1/GluN2B receptors which is attributed to its binding at the ifenprodil-binding site. Furthermore, we found that 7-PhO-THA exhibits a less pronounced inhibitory effect in a voltage-dependent manner on both GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors when the ifenprodil-binding site is either missing or structurally disrupted. We first measured the IC_{50} values using different concentrations of compound **II-52** ($0.3\text{--}300 \mu\text{M}$) and compound **I-52** ($0.3\text{--}100 \mu\text{M}$) at hGluN1/hGluN2A and hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors at membrane potentials of -60 and 40 mV (**Fig. 1A,C,E,G**). Due to the physiological irrelevance, and since some derivatives showed limited ECS solubility, we did not examine concentrations above $300 \mu\text{M}$. In accordance with our measurements of the relative inhibition shown in **Table 1**, we obtained the IC_{50} values of $\sim 3.6 \mu\text{M}$ for compound **II-52** and of $\sim 2.4 \mu\text{M}$ for compound **I-52** on WT hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors at a membrane potential of -60 mV (**Table 2, Fig. 1B,F**). In contrast to 7-PhO-THA, both derivatives showed only a slight voltage-dependent inhibitory effect at WT hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors, as we obtained IC_{50} values of $\sim 6.8 \mu\text{M}$ and $\sim 7.7 \mu\text{M}$ for compounds **II-52** and **I-52**, respectively, at a membrane potential of 40 mV (**Table 2, Fig. 1D,H**). As expected, both derivatives were less potent in the inhibition of WT hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors, with IC_{50} values of $\sim 10.1 \mu\text{M}$ for compound **II-52** and of $\sim 5.1 \mu\text{M}$ for compound **I-52** at a membrane potential of

-60 mV (**Table 2, Fig. 1B,F**). In addition, in the case of hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors, we observed a strong voltage-dependent inhibitory effect of both derivatives with IC_{50} values of $\sim 43.8 \mu\text{M}$ for compound **II-52** and $\sim 25.0 \mu\text{M}$ for compound **I-52** at the membrane potential of 40 mV (**Table 2, Fig. 1D,H**). As in our previous study, we further focused on the ifenprodil-binding site. hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors lacking the ifenprodil-binding site due to amino-terminal domain (ATD) deletion at the GluN1 subunit (hGluN1- Δ ATD/hGluN2B receptors, **Fig. 1A,C,E,G**) demonstrated similar IC_{50} values for compounds **II-52** and **I-52**, at both studied membrane potentials (-60 and 40 mV) to those we observed for WT hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors (**Table 2, Fig. 1B,D,F,H**). We examined only the hGluN1- Δ ATD/hGluN2B receptors, since the transfection of HEK293 cells with the hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors lacking the ATDs of the GluN1 and GluN2B subunits (hGluN1- Δ ATD/hGluN2B- Δ ATD) did not yield functional receptors, as there were no observable current responses induced by 1 mM L-glutamate (data not shown). Taken together, our results indicate that both compounds **II-52** and **I-52** share a similar mechanism of inhibitory action at NMDARs as 7-PhO-THA, although both derivatives exhibit only a mild voltage-dependent effect at WT hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors when compared to 7-PhO-THA.

Finally, we decided to study the interaction of the derivatives with the ifenprodil-binding site using a combination of molecular docking and electrophysiological characterization of mutant hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors. Since compound **II-52** exhibited a higher difference in IC_{50} values between WT hGluN1/hGluN2A and hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors at the membrane potential of -60 mV when compared to compound **I-52** (**Table 2, Fig. 1B,F**), we further analyzed only the inhibitory effect of compound **II-52** on mutant hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors (**Table 2, Fig. 1B,D**). Indeed, a docking study in tandem with molecular dynamics (MD) simulation revealed that compound **II-52** is accommodated at the WT GluN1/GluN2B ATD dimer interface (**Fig. 2**). The binding of compound **II-52** closely resembles the binding topology of ifenprodil, which is another potent inhibitor specific to the GluN2B ATD [16]. Indeed, the hydrogen bond can be considered as the critical interaction between the exocyclic amino group of compound **II-52** and the carbonyl oxygen of the Gln110 residue in the GluN2B subunit (which is pivotal also for the interaction with the piperidine nitrogen of ifenprodil). The most profound π - π interactions can be observed for Phe113 and Tyr109 residues within the GluN1 subunit, providing parallel and distorted stackings to the 2-methoxyphenyl and THA moieties of compound **II-52**, respectively. Besides, the amide backbone of Phe114 and Asp113 residues from the GluN2B subunit is involved in the formation of other hydrogen bonds with the amino group of compound **II-52**. In line with the electrophysiological data (**Table 2**), the slight increase in affinities observed for hGluN1-F113A/hGluN2B receptors is likely a result of the less sterically demanding alanine residue replacing the phenylalanine residue. By contrast, the decrease in the inhibitory activity of compound **II-52** at hGluN1-Y109C/hGluN2B receptors can be attributed to the absence of parallel π - π stacking interactions between the THA core of compound **II-52** and the Cys109 residue within the mutant GluN1 subunit. Finally, in the case of hGluN1/hGluN2B-Q110F receptors, compound **II-52** preserved almost identical inhibitory effect as observed for WT hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors. It is plausible to suggest that equipotency might be coined for formation of an alternative hydrogen bond between the amide group of the Phe110 residue in the GluN2B subunit and the amino group of compound **II-52**.

Table 1. Cytotoxicity and inhibitory effect of 7-PhO-THA derivatives at hAChE, hBChE, and recombinant hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors expressed in HEK293 cells.

Compound	Cytotoxicity	hAChE	hBChE	hGluN1/hGluN2B
	CHO-K1 IC ₅₀ (μM)	IC ₅₀ (μM)	IC ₅₀ (μM)	RI ¹ (1 μM), (%)
I-50	55 ± 3.4	6.42 ± 0.15	2.93 ± 0.08	30.3 ± 1.5
I-51	78 ± 16	28.22 ± 1.29	n.d.	16.6 ± 1.5
I-52	68 ± 0.5	8.52 ± 0.41	5.48 ± 0.19	35.0 ± 1.4
I-53	34 ± 4.7	5.28 ± 0.12	2.81 ± 0.07	18.1 ± 0.7
I-54	85 ± 2.6	5.25 ± 0.20	7.96 ± 0.15	16.0 ± 1.2
I-55	76 ± 5.8	8.36 ± 0.19	7.34 ± 0.20	18.7 ± 1.4
I-56	81 ± 6.1	4.24 ± 0.33	14.50 ± 0.59	22.7 ± 3.3
I-57	28 ± 1.2	5.07 ± 0.08	3.60 ± 0.07	8.7 ± 1.4
I-58	11 ± 0.4	2.78 ± 0.11	3.11 ± 0.07	6.7 ± 1.5
I-59	69 ± 3.5	5.76 ± 0.21	16.51 ± 0.50	9.5 ± 1.6
I-60	39 ± 1.9	3.72 ± 0.12	5.48 ± 0.21	9.6 ± 1.3
II-51	25 ± 3.4	3.78 ± 0.1	4.15 ± 0.11	19.3 ± 2.2
II-52	43 ± 0.5	0.84 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.01	25.7 ± 2.2
II-53	20 ± 0.9	9.19 ± 0.27	3.66 ± 0.04	21.2 ± 1.1
II-54	27 ± 5.2	2.64 ± 0.06	2.76 ± 0.07	14.7 ± 2.1
II-55	20 ± 2.7	3.29 ± 0.08	1.95 ± 0.05	18.0 ± 2.6
II-56	26 ± 2.4	2.90 ± 0.19	7.26 ± 0.24	33.2 ± 3.5

II-57	12 ± 0.9	2.92 ± 0.09	3.32 ± 0.11	14.2 ± 1.2
II-58	5.1 ± 0.3	1.96 ± 0.09	6.61 ± 0.17	16.0 ± 0.6
II-60	13 ± 1.2	1.62 ± 0.06	3.88 ± 0.08	8.2 ± 1.8
III-50	38 ± 2.1	5.36 ± 0.10	1.40 ± 0.05	34.9 ± 3.4
III-51	26 ± 3.1	5.80 ± 0.12	4.17 ± 0.16	8.8 ± 1.3
III-52	74 ± 6	9.62 ± 0.22	5.48 ± 0.21	57.6 ± 2.7
III-53	13 ± 1.5	12.25 ± 0.53	2.74 ± 0.06	14.8 ± 1.2
III-54	21 ± 1.5	4.25 ± 0.11	2.62 ± 0.05	7.1 ± 1.6
III-55	140 ± 0.3	3.79 ± 0.08	2.78 ± 0.10	11.9 ± 0.8
III-56	28 ± 2.1	3.63 ± 0.01	2.74 ± 0.12	29.6 ± 1.9
III-57	90 ± 0.8	4.22 ± 0.11	1.85 ± 0.06	12.0 ± 1.9
III-58	9 ± 1.1	71.63 ± 4.24	2.51 ± 0.11	10.1 ± 1.3
III-60	30 ± 1.2	0.99 ± 0.04	5.27 ± 0.16	7.8 ± 0.8
7-PhO-THA	31 ± 1	2.40 ± 1.8	4.9 ± 3.3	33.1 ± 3.3
THA	303 ± 38	0.32 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.01	0*

¹The relative inhibition (RI) was calculated as the ratio of the steady-state currents induced by 1 mM L-glutamate in the presence and absence of the indicated compounds at a concentration of 1 μM (in %), measured at the membrane potential of -60 mV in HEK293 cells transfected with the hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors (see text for more details). n.d.= 'the IC₅₀ was not determined' – the compound caused 45% inhibition at 100 μM.* not measured for 1 microM, but less than 1 percent for 3 microM

Table 2. The parameters from the dose-response analysis for compounds **II-52** and **I-52** in WT hGluN1/hGluN2A and WT or mutated hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors measured at the membrane potentials of -60 and 40 mV.

Compound	Receptor	IC ₅₀ (-60mV) (μ M)	<i>h</i> (-60 mV)	IC ₅₀ (40 mV) (μ M)	<i>h</i> (40 mV)	<i>n</i> (-60mV) / <i>n</i> (40 mV)
II-52	hGluN1/hGluN2A	10.1 \pm 1.3	1.43 \pm 0.05	43.8 \pm 3.0	1.44 \pm 0.06	8/6
	hGluN1/hGluN2B	3.6 \pm 0.3	1.01 \pm 0.05	6.8 \pm 0.5	1.18 \pm 0.03	12/6
	hGluN1- Δ ATD/hGluN2B	11.1 \pm 1.0	1.55 \pm 0.15	47.2 \pm 1.0	1.65 \pm 0.07	6/5
	hGluN1-F113A/hGluN2B	1.7 \pm 0.1	1.06 \pm 0.03	2.1 \pm 0.1	1.15 \pm 0.06	7/4
	hGluN1-Y109C/hGluN2B	9.5 \pm 0.7	1.10 \pm 0.07	48.4 \pm 4.5	1.35 \pm 0.02	9/4
	hGluN1/hGluN2B-Q110F	4.6 \pm 0.2	1.37 \pm 0.05	10.3 \pm 0.4	1.22 \pm 0.04	6/6
	hGluN1/hGluN2B-F114A	9.4 \pm 1.0	1.70 \pm 0.10	31.9 \pm 1.4	1.55 \pm 0.06	6/12
I-52	hGluN1/hGluN2A	5.1 \pm 0.3	2.61 \pm 0.28	25.0 \pm 2.1	2.00 \pm 0.15	7/5
	hGluN1/hGluN2B	2.4 \pm 0.3	1.35 \pm 0.11	7.7 \pm 0.6	1.42 \pm 0.09	9/6
	hGluN1- Δ ATD/hGluN2B	5.2 \pm 0.6	2.92 \pm 0.21	17.9 \pm 1.1	2.29 \pm 0.04	7/4

The IC₅₀ values and Hill coefficients (*h*) were obtained by fitting the electrophysiology data obtained at indicated membrane potentials using *Equation 1*. Data are presented as the mean \pm SEM (in μ M), and *n* corresponds to the number of analyzed cells.

Figure 1. Compounds II-52 and I-52 inhibit the hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors with higher potency compared to hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors. (A, C, E, G) Representative whole-cell current responses induced by 1 mM L-glutamate (Glu) in HEK293 cells expressing either hGluN1/hGluN2A (left), hGluN1/hGluN2B (middle), or hGluN1-ΔATD/hGluN2B (right) receptors, recorded in the presence of indicated concentrations (in μM) of compound II-52 (A, C) and compound I-52 (E, G) at membrane potentials of -60 mV (A, E) or 40 mV (C, G). (B, D, F, H) Dose-response curves for the inhibitory effect of compound II-52 (B, D) and compound I-52 (F, H) at the indicated NMDARs measured at a membrane potential of -60 mV (B, F) or 40 mV (D, H), obtained by fitting the electrophysiological data using Equation 1. The resulting IC₅₀ values and Hill coefficients are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 2. Predicted position of compound **II-52** at the GluN1/GluN2B ATD dimer interface upon molecular modeling in tandem with MD simulation. **(A)** The 3D structure of GluN1/GluN2B ATD dimer interface in interaction with compound **II-52** was created with The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System (Version 2.4.1, Schrödinger) using the PDB ID: 5EWJ. Compound **II-52** is displayed in green as carbon atoms. Light blue residues belong to the GluN1 subunit, whereas purple residues are ascribed to the GluN2B subunit. Distances are provided in angstroms (Å). **(B)** The 2D view of compound **II-52** in interaction with the residues from GluN1/GluN2B NTD dimer interface was generated with Maestro 12.3 (Schrödinger). Line color interactions delineate a specific type of interaction (green for π - π stacking interaction, purple for hydrogen bond).

***In vivo* pharmacokinetic and toxicity study**

Based on all the *in vitro* data obtained, we selected the following candidates for the *in vivo* analysis: *i)* compounds **I-52**, **III-52** and **III-56** as the most effective NMDAR inhibitors, and *ii)* compound **II-52** as the derivative with potent dual inhibitory action at both the hAChE and NMDARs. From a structural point of view, all the compounds are substituted with a methoxy-group either in position 2 (in the case of compounds **I-52**, **II-52**, and **III-52**) or in position 4 (for compound **III-56**) of the phenoxy residue. For those four compounds, the ability to cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB) has been evaluated. The ability to cross the BBB and enter the brain is the main prerequisite for drugs targeting CNS disorders. For pharmacokinetic evaluation, the rat model has been used. The levels of the compounds were assessed at two time points, namely the 15th and 60th minute. The data confirm the ability to cross the BBB for all the tested compounds following *i.p.* administration at a dose of 5 mg/kg, although not all to a similar extent (**Fig. 3**). Whereas compounds **II-52** and **III-52** showed limited ability to cross the BBB, compound **III-56** demonstrated an unlimited ability to enter the brain as evidenced by its presence in both plasma and the brain at equivalent levels. Interestingly, compound **I-52** showed substantially higher levels in the brain compared to plasma, which points to an involvement of an active transporter enhancing brain permeation. The same ability to accumulate in the brain has been reported for THA [16], but not for 7-PhO-THA [16]. Due to the high anti-NMDA potency, high bioavailability, and BBB permeability, we selected compound **I-52** for subsequent experiments. Compound **II-52** was also selected due to good BBB permeability and highly potent dual action against both NMDAR and hAChE.

Prior to conducting the behavioral studies, it was essential to establish the dose at which no side effects occurred, referred to as the NOAEL (No-Observed-Adverse-Effect Level). Compound **I-52** exhibited no

side effects at a dose of 10 mg/kg when administered *i.p.* However, at a dose of 20 mg/kg, a temporary (for 10-15 min) loss of activity was observed. Compound **II-52** was found to be safe at a dose of 5 mg/kg, but at the dose of 10 mg/kg, a reduction in breathing and a loss of activity were observed. This observation could potentially be attributed to the higher anti-hAChE activity of compound **II-52**, which might be responsible for these side effects even at lower doses.

Figure 3. Concentration of the selected compounds in plasma and brain at the 15th and 60th minute time intervals after 5mg/kg *i.p.* in rats. Results are shown as mean \pm SEM (n=3).

Microsomal stability and biotransformation of compounds I-52 and II-52

To investigate the drug-likeness of compounds **I-52** and **II-52**, human liver microsomal (HLM) stabilities were examined. To this end we used the standards diazepam and verapamil with low and high metabolic clearance respectively, and compared their HLM stability after 45 min of incubation with that of the selected lead candidates **I-52** and **II-52** (Table 3). In line with the literature, microsomal stability of verapamil displayed high intrinsic clearance ($CL_{int} = 71.27 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$) and short half-life ($T_{1/2} = 19.47$ min), whereas diazepam exerted low metabolic clearance ($CL_{int} = 0.80 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$) and long half-life ($T_{1/2} = 1732.50$ min) [16]. Hit compound **II-52** revealed relatively high metabolic stability as expressed by HLM $T_{1/2}$ and CL_{int} , showing 3.5 times higher microsomal stability than that of verapamil, but 24x lower compared to diazepam. On the other hand, compound **I-52** showed two times lower HLM stability compared to **II-52**. Both of the tested compound can be classified as compounds with medium clearance with respect to phase I metabolic deactivation [28]. Assuming that clearance of these compounds

follows first-order kinetics, it can be expected that they do not accumulate in the body when properly dosed, whilst being stable enough to exert their pharmacodynamic effect.

With the biotransformation-toxicity pathway of tacrine in mind, the amount of 7-OH-TA formed after incubation with HLM was also determined. We calculated the sum of the areas of all detected metabolites and expressed the relative amount of 7-OH-TA metabolite. Indeed, 3.24 % of 7-OH-TA was formed from compound **II-52**, whereas only 0.009 % from compound **I-52**. These results revealed that the amount of 7-OH-TA formed from both these compounds is significantly less than in the biotransformation of tacrine, where approximately 30 % of this metabolite is formed (Novak, Svobodova et al. 2023). In addition, the amount of 7-OH-TA formed from **I-52** appears to be negligible from the hepatotoxicity point of view according to this hypothesis.

Table 3. Microsomal stability expressed as microsomal half-life ($T_{1/2}$) and intrinsic clearance (CL_{int}) for selected compounds **I-52** and **II-52**. Diazepam and verapamil were included as reference drugs with low and high intrinsic clearance, respectively.

Compound	HLM $T_{1/2}$ (min)	Human CL_{int} ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$)	Amount of all formed metabolites (Sum of the areas)	7-OH-TA (area)	Relative representation of 7-OH-TA (%)
verapamil	19.47	71.27	--	--	--
diazepam	1732.5	0.80	--	--	--
I-52	69.3	20.02	10.02×10^8	9.27×10^4	0.00925
II-52	161.16	8.61	8.26×10^8	2.68×10^7	3.24

Pharmacodynamic *in vivo* effects of compounds **I-52** and **II-52**

We further assessed the *in vivo* pharmacodynamic effects of compounds **I-52** and **II-52** through *i.p.* administration in rats. Firstly, the risk of behavioral side effects characteristic for NMDAR antagonists was evaluated. Next, their pro-cognitive effects in the animal model of cognitive deficit based on disruption of the cholinergic neurotransmitter system were investigated. Finally, the most promising compound from the point of view of high efficacy and low toxicity, i.e. the compound **I-52**, was selected for assessment of its neuroprotective effect in an animal model of neurodegeneration induced by overstimulation of NMDARs.

Since the comparison of the *in vivo* effects of compounds **I-52** and **II-52** is complicated by their different BBB penetration, these compounds were administered at different doses (2 mg/kg and 5 mg/kg, respectively) in all behavioral tests, in an attempt to overcome the different brain availability i.e. to ensure similar brain levels. Of note, such doses are considered to be safe according to the acute toxicity assessment (NOAEL dose).

Evaluation of behavioral side effects of compounds **I-52** and **II-52**

Some NMDAR antagonists interfere with physiological neurotransmission, resulting in induction of serious psychotomimetic side effects limiting their clinical use [29]. Screening of behavioral side effects hence represents an integral part of preclinical studies focused on NMDAR antagonists. In rats, psychotomimetic effects are expressed, among others, as a hyperlocomotion in the open-field test and a deficit of pre-pulse inhibition of startle response [30]. Therefore, the effects of compounds **I-52** and **II-52** on the behavior of rats were evaluated and compared with the effects of the prototypical high-affinity NMDAR antagonist, MK-801. Analysis of distance moved in the open-field test revealed differences between treatment groups (ANOVA, $F(3, 21) = 80.370$, $p < 0.0001$). Animals treated with MK-801 (0.2 mg/kg) demonstrated marked hyperlocomotion compared to vehicle-treated animals ($p < 0.0001$), while the locomotor activity of animals treated with either compound **I-52** or **II-52** did not differ from that of control (**Fig. 4A**). Analysis of the pre-pulse inhibition of acoustic startle response (ANOVA, $F(3, 21) = 4.113$, $p = 0.0192$) and subsequent *post hoc* test showed that MK-801 disrupted the pre-pulse inhibition ($p = 0.0339$ in comparison to vehicle). On the other hand, the pre-pulse inhibition of animals treated with compound **I-52** or **II-52** was not disrupted, as it did not differ from the vehicle-treated group (**Fig. 4B**). Taken together, the results indicate that unlike MK-801, compounds **I-52** and **II-52** at the selected doses of 2 mg/kg and 5 mg/kg, respectively, possess low risk of NMDA-associated behavioral side effects. On the other hand, the observed psychotomimetic effects of MK-801 are consistent with the literature [30, 31].

Figure 4. The effects of compounds **I-52** and **II-52** on locomotor activity in the open-field test and on the pre-pulse inhibition of acoustic startle response (**A,B**). Graphs show the distance (in meters) moved by the animal in the open-field test (**A**) and the ratio (in %) of the pre-pulse inhibition of the startle response (PPI) induced by acoustic stimuli (**B**) after *i.p.* administration of either vehicle (VEH) or MK-801 (0.2 mg/kg in the open-field test and 0.3 mg/kg in the pre-pulse inhibition test), compound **I-52** (2 mg/kg), or compound **II-52** (5 mg/kg). Data are presented as the mean + SEM, $n \geq 6$, * $p < 0.0500$, **** $p < 0.0001$ vs. VEH (ANOVA).

Effects of compounds **I-52** and **II-52** in the scopolamine-induced model of cognitive deficit

To evaluate whether compounds **I-52** and **II-52** display pro-cognitive effects *in vivo*, a model of cognitive deficit induced by the muscarinic acetylcholine receptor antagonist scopolamine was used. Scopolamine and the studied drugs were co-administered *i.p.* daily before the experiment and the cognition of the animals was tested in the Morris water maze (day 1–4: stable hidden platform position – 8 training trials daily, day 4: probe trial).

Two-way repeated measures ANOVA of the latencies to find the platform during the training days revealed significant effects of treatment ($F(3, 19) = 13.93, p < 0.0001$) and testing day ($F(2.478, 47.08) = 24.28, p < 0.0001$), with no interaction. The *post hoc* test revealed that scopolamine considerably increased the latency to find the platform, indicating cognitive deficit ($p < 0.0001$ vs. vehicle). Similarly, the animals co-treated with compound **II-52** and scopolamine displayed longer latency than vehicle-treated animals ($p < 0.0001$), indicating no amelioration of the scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit. Conversely, the latency in the animals co-treated with compound **I-52** and scopolamine was significantly shorter than the latency in the scopolamine-treated animals ($p = 0.0125$), clearly indicating that compound **I-52** mitigated the scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit (**Fig. 5A**).

Nevertheless, even rats with cognitive deficit may adopt suboptimal non-spatial search strategies (e.g. circling at a fixed distance of the pool wall), resulting in reduced latency, while not reflecting true knowledge of the platform location. Therefore, we also analyzed the mean distance of the rat from the platform (proximity; in cm) during the trial, which represents a better measure of spatial memory according to some authors [32]. The analysis gave similar results as the analysis of latency (two-way repeated measures ANOVA; the treatment effect $F(3, 19) = 11.73, p = 0.0001$; the testing day effect $F(2.008, 38.16) = 26.98, p < 0.0001$; with no interaction). The animals treated with scopolamine (mean \pm SEM = 71.6 ± 3.6) and co-treated with scopolamine and compound **II-52** (78.7 ± 3.5) demonstrated increased mean distance from the platform ($p < 0.0001$ vs. vehicle for both). Conversely, the animals co-treated with compound **I-52** and scopolamine (59.5 ± 4.6) did not differ from the vehicle-treated animals (51.7 ± 1.5) and showed shorter mean distance from the platform than scopolamine-treated animals ($p = 0.0264$; data not shown). It suggests that compound **I-52** not only restored normal performance in the Morris water maze in terms of escape latency, but it was also associated with the optimal true spatial strategy characteristic for healthy animals [32].

On day 4, after finishing the training trials, the platform was removed and a probe trial was performed. The analysis (Kruskal–Wallis test) of the number of crossings of the area where the platform was originally located indicated a significant effect of the treatment ($H = 10.94, N_{\text{VEH}} = 6, N_{\text{SCOP}} = 6, N_{\text{I-52 + SCOP}} = 6, N_{\text{II-52 + SCOP}} = 5; p = 0.0120$). The animals treated with scopolamine or co-treated with scopolamine and compound **II-52** showed a decreased number of platform crossings in comparison to the animals treated with vehicle ($p = 0.0464$ and 0.0238 , respectively), while the animals co-treated with compound **I-52** and scopolamine did not differ from the vehicle-treated group, which is consistent with amelioration of the cognitive deficit (**Fig. 5B**). The swim patterns of the animals during the probe trial are depicted in **Fig. 5C**, illustrating the preference of the animals treated with vehicle and mainly also of the animals co-treated with compound **I-52** and scopolamine for the place where the platform was originally located.

Taken together, compound **I-52** (2 mg/kg) but not compound **II-52** (5 mg/kg) was able to mitigate scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit. The observed impairing effect of scopolamine on reference memory in the Morris water maze is in accordance with the literature [33–35]. Various AChE inhibitors can ameliorate the scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit, often showing an inverted U-shaped dose-

response effect [33]. The pro-cognitive effect of compound **I-52** may therefore be caused by its hAChE-inhibiting properties. However, it is not fully clear why compound **I-52** had beneficial effect, while compound **II-52** did not. It is important to note that the compounds display not only different affinities for hAChE and hBChE (those of compound **I-52** being lower), but also different BBB penetration (that of compound **I-52** being higher). Therefore, the resulting level of inhibition of brain cholinesterases *in vivo* is unclear, making it impossible to assess the role of the level of AChE inhibition in the different behavioral effects of the tested compounds. Moreover, the NMDAR-inhibiting effects of the compounds may also contribute to the mitigation of scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit. NMDAR antagonists, MK-801 [36] and memantine [37], were found to increase acetylcholine release in certain brain structures which speaks in favor of the positive effect of compound **I-52** being more effective against NMDARs than **II-52** (Table 1 and 2). Indeed, when memantine was co-administered with the AChE inhibitor donepezil, they had synergistic effects on acetylcholine release [37], and memantine co-administered with the AChE inhibitor galantamine displayed synergistic effects in attenuating scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit [38].

It is therefore unclear whether the positive effect of compound **I-52** is a result of both its AChE as well as NMDAR modulating effects. To further elucidate its beneficial effect through the NMDARs, a neuroprotection study in the NMDA-induced *in vivo* model of neurodegeneration was conducted.

Figure 5. The effects of compounds **I-52** and **II-52** on the performance of model animals with scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit in the Morris water maze test. Upper left (**A**) graph shows the escape latency (in seconds) of animal during the training trials after *i.p.* administration of either the vehicle (VEH), or scopolamine (2 mg/kg; SCOP), or co-administration of scopolamine with compound **I-52** (2 mg/kg; I-52 + SCOP) or compound **II-52** (5 mg/kg; II-52 + SCOP). Data are presented as the mean + SEM, $n \geq 5$; * $p < 0.0500$, **** $p < 0.0001$ vs. VEH; # $p < 0.0500$, ##### $p < 0.0001$ vs. SCOP (two-way

repeated measures ANOVA). Upper right (**B**) graph shows the number of platform area crossings by animals in the probe trial. Individual animal's values are plotted over box plots (median with 25th–75th percentile) with whiskers indicating minimum and maximum. * $p < 0.05$ vs. VEH (Kruskal–Wallis test). Bottom (**C**) The heatmaps of the animals' search behavior in the pool during the probe trial (merged per treatment group). The left picture shows the position of the platform (circle) and the starting position of animals (arrow). Colors represent the proportion of track occupied by the animals in that location (blue = low, red = high).

Neuroprotective effect of compound I-52 on NMDA-induced lesion of the dorsal hippocampus

Intra-hippocampal injection of NMDA results in long-lasting degeneration of glutamatergic neurons in the rat hippocampus, especially in the CA1, CA3, the dentate gyrus, hilus and surrounding nervous tissue [39]. Compound **I-52** was selected for testing of its neuroprotective activity against NMDA-induced lesion in the dorsal hippocampus, based on its promising outcomes from previous behavioral experiments. We infused a mixed solution of 25 mM NMDA and 30 μ M of compound **I-52** into the rat dorsal hippocampus and analyzed a number of Fluoro-Jade B (FJB)-positive cells in the evaluated areas (**Fig. 6**). Analysis of the total scores of hippocampal damage ($F(2, 25) = 36.49$, $p < 0.0001$; ANOVA) and subsequent *post hoc* test revealed increased damage score in the animals treated with NMDA and vehicle ($p < 0.0001$) in comparison to animals treated with PBS and vehicle, confirming that NMDA induced extensive hippocampal damage. On the other hand, animals co-treated with NMDA and compound **I-52** displayed significantly lower damage scores than those treated with NMDA and vehicle ($p = 0.0024$), clearly demonstrating the neuroprotective effect of compound **I-52** against neurodegeneration induced by overstimulation of NMDARs.

Hence, compound **I-52** demonstrates a similar mode of action to the 7-substituted THA-based compounds that we had previously examined [12, 33]. Indeed, both **I-52** and the previously tested compounds showed a neuroprotective effect in the animal model of NMDA-induced lesion. This finding aligns with the neuroprotective effects observed for other dual-acting 6-substituted THA-based compounds within the glutamate toxicity model in rat primary cortical neurons [40]. Previously, also bis(7)-THA demonstrated a neuroprotective effect in the animal model of acute focal cerebral ischemic insult [15]. Nevertheless, bis(7)-THA is associated with hepatotoxic side effects [41], which we have addressed through our rational design approach.

In summary, the neuroprotective effect of compound **I-52** can be clearly attributed to its interaction with NMDARs, while an effect through AChE inhibition as well as potential involvement of other receptor systems cannot be ruled out[10].

Figure 6. The neuroprotective effect of compound **I-52** on the NMDA-induced model of hippocampal neurodegeneration. **(A)** Representative images of brain slices from animals that were injected with a solution containing either PBS and vehicle (PBS+VEH; control), or NMDA and vehicle (25 mM; NMDA +VEH), or NMDA and compound **I-52** (30 μ M; NMDA + I-52). **(B)** The graph shows the total scores of damaged cells within the hippocampus 24 h post-application of the indicated solutions, determined based on the FJB staining for neurodegenerative cells. Data are presented as the mean + SEM; $n \geq 9$; ** $p < 0.0100$, *** $p < 0.0010$, **** $p < 0.0001$ vs. PBS + VEH (ANOVA).

Conclusion

Through the rational design of 30 novel derivatives, we have systematically explored the chemical space surrounding the hit compound 7-PhO-THA. Our primary objectives were to lower hepatotoxicity while promoting their dual effect, with emphasis on the antagonism on the GluN1/GluN2B receptor. All the compounds demonstrated the ability to inhibit the cholinesterases and NMDAR in various efficacy. Employing the down-selection process based on all the *in vitro* data obtained, we selected compounds **I-52**, **III-52** and **III-56** as the most effective NMDAR inhibitors, together with compound **II-52** as a highly effective AChE blocker representative. The selection was further narrowed by BBB permeability *in vivo* to the final candidates **I-52** and **II-52**. Despite the difference in AChE-inhibitory action, using

hGluN1/hGluN2B mutants and *in silico* studies we showed that both compounds share a mechanism of inhibitory action at NMDARs similar to that of 7-PhO-THA, i.e. a selectivity towards hGluN1/hGluN2B subtype, thanks to interaction with the ifendprodil-binding site, although both derivatives exhibit only a mild voltage-dependent effect. Both compounds also lacked the behavioral side effects frequently observed with high-affinity NMDAR ligands. However in a scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit test, in contrast to the minor ability to block AChE, we have identified compound **I-52** as a lead candidate with favorable behavioral and neuroprotective effects under various *in vivo* models. Importantly, this lead drug candidate also showed low hepatotoxicity as demonstrated by the biotransformation study; such toxicity is frequently observed in THA-based compounds.

Methods

1. General methods and chemistry

All chemical solvents and reagents were used in the highest available purity without further purification. They were purchased from Merck (Prague, Czech Republic) or FluoroChem (Dublin, Ireland). The reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel plates (60 F254, Merck, Prague, Czech Republic) and the spots were visualized by ultraviolet light (254 nm). Purification of crude products was carried out using columns of silica gel (silica gel 100, 0.063-0.200 mm, 70-230 mesh ASTM, Fluka, Prague, Czech Republic) and PuriFlash GEN5 column, 5.250 (Interchim, Montluçon, France; silica gel 100, 60 Å, 230–400 mesh ASTM, Merck). Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were recorded in deuterated chloroform (CDCl₃), deuterated methanol (CD₃OD), and deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Bruker Avance NEO 500 MHz spectrometer (499.87 MHz for ¹H NMR and 125.71 MHz for ¹³C NMR). Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) and spin multiplicities are given as singlet (s), broad singlet (bs), doublet (d), doublet of doublet (dd), triplet (t), quartet (q), pentet (p), or multiplet (m). Coupling constants (*J*) are reported in Hz. The synthesized compounds were analyzed by a liquid chromatography – mass spectrometry (LC-MS) system consisting of UHPLC Dionex Ultimate 3000 RS coupled with Q Exactive Plus mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) to obtain high-resolution mass spectra. Melting points were measured using an automated melting point recorder M-565 (Büchi, Switzerland) and are uncalibrated. Gradient LC-UV analysis confirmed > 95% purity for all the final compounds.

1.1. Chemistry

1.1.1. General procedure for the preparation of compounds **8-13** and **14-19**

Compounds **8-13** and **14-19** were synthesized according to the method shown in **Scheme S1**. A 50 mL round-bottom flask filled with an inert argon atmosphere was charged with commercially available starting materials: compound **1-6** (4.6 mmol; 1.0 eq), *N*-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetamide (compound **7**; 5.5 mmol; 1.2 eq), Cs₂CO₃ (9.2 mmol; 2.0 eq), CuBr (5-10 mol%), and 1-(2-pyridinyl)acetone (0.92 mmol; 0.2 eq). Anhydrous DMSO (5 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 90 °C for 24 h. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature. Subsequently, ethyl acetate (EA) was added to the mixture, and the resulting precipitate was filtered under reduced pressure through a sintered glass filter. The filtrate was evaporated *in vacuo* and extracted between

dichloromethane (DCM; 3 × 50 mL) and water (100 mL). The organic fractions were combined, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure, and the residue purified by flash chromatography, eluting with DCM/MeOH/25% aqueous NH₃ (20:1:0.1) to give intermediates **8-13**. These intermediates were placed into a microwave reactor tube and hydrolysed by reaction with KOH (27.3 mmol; 7.5 eq) in 5 mL of MeOH/H₂O (2:1). The reaction conditions were set at 160 °C at a maximum power of 150 W with a dynamic curve, for 90 min. The reaction mixture was purified without any work-up by flash chromatography, eluting with DCM/MeOH/25% aqueous NH₃ (9:1:0.1) to give compounds **14-19**.

1.1.1.1. *N*-[4-(2-methylphenoxy)phenyl]acetamide (8)

Yield 79%. Orange viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.46 (bs, 1H); 7.34 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H); 7.17 – 7.13 (m, 1H); 7.10 – 7.04 (m, 1H); 7.00 – 6.94 (m, 1H); 6.80 – 6.74 (m, 3H); 2.15 (s, 3H); 2.07 (s, 3H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 168.46; 154.71; 154.38; 132.64; 131.45; 129.73; 127.13; 123.88; 121.89; 119.30; 117.89; 24.37; 16.18 ppm.

1.1.1.2. *N*-[4-(3-methylphenoxy)phenyl]acetamide (9)

Yield 36%. Brown solid; orange viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.57 (bs, 1H); 7.49 – 7.45 (m, 2H); 7.21 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H); 7.00 – 6.96 (m, 2H); 6.94 – 6.90 (m, 1H); 6.83 – 6.77 (m, 2H); 2.34 (s, 3H); 2.19 (s, 3H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 168.50; 157.47; 153.65; 139.95; 133.29; 129.45; 123.94; 121.81; 119.55; 119.12; 115.49; 24.38; 21.40 ppm.

1.1.1.3. *N*-[4-(3-methoxyphenoxy)phenyl]acetamide (10)

Yield 21%. Orange viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.47 (s, 1H), 7.43 – 7.39 (m, 2H), 6.97 – 6.93 (m, 2H), 6.92 – 6.85 (m, 4H), 3.80 (s, 3H), 2.16 (s, 3H). ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 168.33, 155.74, 154.86, 150.40, 132.63, 121.78, 120.35, 118.16, 114.81, 55.62, 24.30 ppm.

1.1.1.4. *N*-[4-(4-*tert*-butylphenoxy)phenyl]acetamide (11)

Yield 55%. Brown viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.38 – 7.34 (m, 2H); 7.31 (bs, 1H); 7.27 – 7.23 (m, 2H); 6.91 – 6.87 (m, 2H); 6.85 – 6.81 (m, 2H); 2.09 (s, 3H); 1.24 (s, 9H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 168.36; 154.99; 153.92; 146.03; 133.10; 126.54; 121.75; 119.32; 118.03; 34.30; 31.50; 24.42 ppm.

1.1.1.5. *N*-[4-(4-acetylphenoxy)phenyl]acetamide (12)

Yield 40%. Brown viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.87 – 7.83 (m, 2H); 7.74 (bs, 1H); 7.51 – 7.46 (m, 2H); 6.97 – 6.93 (m, 2H); 6.92 – 6.87 (m, 2H); 2.50 (s, 3H); 2.12 (s, 3H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 196.84; 168.52; 162.26; 151.44; 134.89; 131.76; 130.61; 121.71; 120.80; 116.92; 41.01; 30.16; 26.47; 24.44 ppm.

1.1.1.6. *N*-[4-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)phenyl]acetamide (13)

Yield 30%. Orange viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.41 – 7.36 (m, 2H); 6.82 – 6.77 (m, 2H); 6.63 – 6.61 (m, 1H); 6.47 – 6.42 (m, 2H); 2.55 (s, 3H); 2.15 – 2.13 (m, 6H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 170.10; 157.60; 153.64; 139.39; 133.85; 124.37; 121.53; 118.84; 115.74; 39.04; 22.26; 19.97 ppm.

1.1.1.7. 4-(2-methylphenoxy)aniline (14)

Yield 75%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 122.5-123.4 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.14 – 7.11 (m, 1H); 7.03 – 6.98 (m, 1H); 6.91 – 6.87 (m, 1H); 6.73 – 6.67 (m, 3H); 6.60 – 6.56 (m, 2H); 2.20 (s, 3H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 156.32; 149.68; 141.98; 131.23; 128.76; 126.92; 122.70; 119.85; 117.45; 116.37; 16.31 ppm.

1.1.1.8. 4-(3-methylphenoxy)aniline (15)

Yield 85%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 135.5-136.4 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.08 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H); 6.82 – 6.77 (m, 2H); 6.77 – 6.74 (m, 1H); 6.68 – 6.64 (m, 2H); 6.64 – 6.60 (m, 2H); 2.22 (s, 3H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 158.82; 148.97; 142.09; 139.70; 129.27; 122.97; 121.11; 117.95; 116.48; 114.33; 21.44 ppm.

1.1.1.9. 4-(4-methoxyphenoxy)aniline (16)

Yield 88%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 125.4-126.7 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.85 – 6.81 (m, 2H); 6.78 – 6.72 (m, 4H); 6.62 – 6.57 (m, 2H); 3.71 (s, 3H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 155.11; 152.00; 150.38; 141.53; 119.93; 119.16; 116.48; 114.71; 55.70 ppm.

1.1.1.10. 4-(4-*tert*-butylphenoxy)aniline (17)

Yield 75%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 127.5-128.4 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.23 – 7.19 (m, 2H); 6.81 – 6.76 (m, 4H); 6.62 – 6.58 (m, 2H); 1.22 (s, 9H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 156.44; 148.94; 144.86; 142.43; 126.28; 120.93; 116.71; 116.20; 34.16; 31.49 ppm.

1.1.1.11. 1-[4-(4-aminophenoxy)phenyl]ethan-1-one (18)

Yield 24%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 147.5-149.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.96 – 7.91 (m, 1H); 6.94 – 6.90 (m, 2H); 6.87 – 6.83 (m, 2H); 6.80 – 6.76 (m, 2H); 2.54 (s, 3H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 196.70; 163.31; 147.00; 143.66; 131.18; 130.55; 121.79; 116.28; 116.14; 26.42 ppm.

1.1.1.12. 4-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)aniline (19)

Yield 67%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 124.5-125.7 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.68 – 6.64 (m, 2H); 6.64 – 6.60 (m, 2H); 6.54 – 6.51 (m, 1H); 6.38 – 6.35 (m, 2H); 2.10 (s, 6H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 159.03; 148.68; 143.36; 139.04; 123.31; 120.45; 116.39; 114.50; 20.01 ppm.

1.1.2. General procedure for the preparation of compounds I-III 28-38

The 4-phenoxyanilines (compounds **14-19**; 1.0 eq.) or commercially available compounds **20-24** (1.0 eq.) were weighed into a 250 mL distillation flask and toluene (50 mL) and 0.1 g of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (PTSA) were added. Ethyl 2-oxocycloalkancarboxylate (compounds **25-27**; 1.1 eq.) was then added and the flask fitted with a Dean-Stark condenser. The cyclo-condensation reaction was carried out by refluxing in an oil bath at 150 °C for 24 h. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo* and diphenyl ether (10.0 eq.) added to the reaction mixture. The mixture was refluxed at 220-240 °C for 20 min in a metal block under the Dean-Stark condenser. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, and about 30 mL of heptane was then added. The resulting precipitate was filtered under reduced pressure through sintered glass. The residue on the sintered glass was washed three

times with 20 mL of heptane. Intermediates I-III **28-38** were purified by flash chromatography using DCM/MeOH/25% aqueous NH₃ (20:1:0.1).

1.1.2.1. 7-phenoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9(4H)-one (I-28)

Yield: 68%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.99 (bs, 1H); 7.57 – 7.50 (m, 2H); 7.43 – 7.35 (m, 3H); 7.18 – 7.13 (m, 1H); 7.05 – 7.01 (m, 2H); 2.96 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H); 2.66 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.06 – 1.96 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 173.59; 157.01; 154.07; 152.46; 136.67; 130.34; 126.22; 123.76; 123.52; 120.37; 119.14; 118.93; 112.00; 31.97; 27.75; 21.64 ppm.

1.1.2.2. 7-(2-methylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-29)

Yield: 57%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 12.04 (bs, 1H); 7.60 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.43 – 7.39 (m, 2H); 7.37 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H); 7.31 – 7.27 (m, 1H); 7.21 – 7.17 (m, 1H); 7.00 – 6.97 (m, 1H); 3.02 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H); 2.70 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.22 (s, 3H); 2.11 – 2.02 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 173.70; 154.48; 154.16; 153.51; 136.42; 132.12; 129.74; 128.05; 126.43; 124.86; 122.70; 120.55; 120.23; 119.27; 110.07; 32.21; 28.02; 21.91; 16.29 ppm.

1.1.2.3. 7-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-30)

Yield: 35%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. Given its limited solubility, compound **I-30** was used directly for the next step without additional analysis.

1.1.2.4. 7-(3-methylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-31)

Yield: 41%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 12.01 (bs, 1H); 7.58 – 7.52 (m, 1H); 7.52 – 7.47 (m, 1H); 7.41 – 7.34 (m, 1H); 7.31 – 7.25 (m, 1H); 6.98 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H); 6.88 – 6.79 (m, 2H); 2.98 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.67 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.29 (s, 3H); 2.03 (p, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 173.76; 157.34; 154.33; 152.83; 140.31; 136.87; 130.29; 126.47; 124.78; 123.79; 120.55; 119.69; 119.36; 116.24; 112.34; 32.23; 28.01; 21.91; 21.40 ppm.

1.1.2.5. 7-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-32)

Yield: 7%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 12.01 (bs, 1H); 7.57 – 7.54 (m, 2H); 7.40 – 7.36 (m, 1H); 7.32 – 7.27 (m, 1H); 6.77 – 6.72 (m, 1H); 6.63 – 6.60 (m, 1H); 6.59 – 6.54 (m, 1H); 3.74 (s, 3H); 2.98 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.67 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.04 (p, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 173.80; 161.23; 158.56; 154.37; 152.51; 136.98; 131.06; 126.48; 123.85; 120.55; 119.42; 112.59; 111.03; 109.68; 105.22; 55.75; 32.23; 28.02; 21.90 ppm.

1.1.2.6. 7-(4-methylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-33)

Yield: 50%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.94 (bs, 1H); 7.52 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.45 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H); 7.35 (dd, *J* = 8.9; 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.21 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 2H); 6.96 – 6.92 (m, 2H); 2.96 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H); 2.65 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.30 (s, 3H); 2.06 – 1.97 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 173.47; 154.56; 153.87; 153.12; 136.37; 133.09; 130.67; 126.12; 123.14; 120.16; 119.27; 119.01; 111.25; 31.96; 27.77; 21.62; 20.47 ppm.

1.1.2.7. 7-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-34)

Yield: 50%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.96 (s, 1H); 7.52 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.45 (d, *J* = 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.35 (dd, *J* = 8.9, 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.21 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz,

2H); 6.96 – 6.91 (m, 2H); 2.96 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H); 2.65 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H); 2.30 (s, 3H); 2.02 (p, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 173.76, 156.22, 154.27, 154.09, 150.00, 136.39, 126.42, 122.88, 121.32, 120.42, 119.24, 115.64, 110.47, 55.89, 32.21, 28.03, 21.90 ppm.

1.1.2.8. 7-(4-chlorophenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-35)

Yield: 19%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 11.99 (s, 1H); 7.55 – 7.54 (m, 1H); 7.45 – 7.42 (m, 2H); 7.39 – 7.36 (m, 1H); 7.07 – 7.03 (m, 2H); 7.01 – 6.98 (m, 1H); 2.97 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H); 2.66 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H); 2.02 (p, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 173.47; 156.12; 154.17; 151.98; 136.95; 130.19; 127.47; 126.24; 123.54; 120.43; 119.27; 118.88; 112.56; 31.97; 27.72; 21.69 ppm.

1.1.2.9. 7-(4-tert-butylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-36)

Yield: 27%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 11.99 (bs, 1H); 7.58 – 7.32 (m, 5H); 7.00 – 6.94 (m, 2H); 3.01 – 2.95 (m, 2H); 2.70 – 2.61 (m, 2H); 2.09 – 1.96 (m, 2H); 1.30 (s, 9H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 173.79; 154.82; 154.26; 153.16; 146.45; 136.74; 127.27; 126.46; 123.61; 121.21; 120.52; 119.33; 118.90; 115.32; 111.82; 34.56; 32.22; 31.73; 28.01; 21.90 ppm.

1.1.2.10. 7-(4-acetylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-37)

Yield: 33%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 12.07 (bs, 1H); 8.02 – 7.97 (m, 2H); 7.66 – 7.64 (m, 1H); 7.62 – 7.58 (m, 1H); 7.46 – 7.42 (m, 1H); 7.10 – 7.06 (m, 2H); 2.99 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H); 2.68 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H); 2.55 (s, 3H); 2.09 – 2.01 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 196.93; 173.75; 161.86; 154.60; 151.01; 137.65; 132.36; 131.25; 126.59; 124.51; 120.88; 119.63; 117.81; 114.24; 32.27; 28.02; 27.04; 21.89 ppm.

1.1.2.11. 7-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H,4H,9H-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-9-one (I-38)

Yield: 25%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 11.42 (bs, 1H); 7.57 – 7.30 (m, 3H); 6.79 (s, 1H); 6.62 (s, 2H); 3.17 (s, 1H); 2.70 (s, 2H); 2.24 (s, 6H); 1.72 (d, $J = 33.0$ Hz, 4H); 1.23 (s, 1H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 173.79; 157.40; 154.29; 152.89; 139.91; 136.84; 126.49; 125.60; 123.81; 120.51; 119.35; 116.79; 112.40; 32.23; 28.02; 21.92; 21.35 ppm.

1.1.2.12. 7-(2-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-29)

Yield: 49%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 11.39 (bs, 1H); 7.55 – 7.48 (m, 1H); 7.39 – 7.31 (m, 2H); 7.28 – 7.21 (m, 2H); 7.17 – 7.10 (m, 1H); 6.95 – 6.89 (m, 1H); 2.74 – 2.65 (m, 2H); 2.42 – 2.34 (m, 2H); 2.17 (s, 3H); 1.79 – 1.62 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 175.61; 154.51; 153.17; 146.98; 135.56; 132.12; 129.72; 128.04; 124.84; 124.48; 123.17; 120.20; 120.16; 115.28; 109.87; 27.57; 22.36; 22.19; 21.98; 16.29 ppm.

1.1.2.13. 7-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-30)

Yield: 51%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 11.36 (bs, 1H); 7.52 – 7.44 (m, 1H); 7.36 – 7.29 (m, 1H); 7.28 – 7.16 (m, 3H); 7.11 – 7.04 (m, 1H); 7.03 – 6.96 (m, 1H); 3.72 (s, 3H); 2.73 – 2.65 (m, 2H); 2.43 – 2.32 (m, 2H); 1.81 – 1.61 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 175.63; 153.87; 151.90; 146.86; 144.18; 135.30; 126.19; 124.38; 122.51; 122.35; 121.66; 119.80; 115.13; 114.06; 108.63; 56.09; 27.56; 22.37; 22.19; 21.99 ppm.

1.1.2.14. 7-(3-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-31)

Yield: 25%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.36 (bs, 1H); 7.49 – 7.43 (m, 1H); 7.40 – 7.37 (m, 1H); 7.33 – 7.27 (m, 1H); 7.24 – 7.18 (m, 1H); 6.94 – 6.89 (m, 1H); 6.80 – 6.73 (m, 2H); 2.63 (t, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 2H); 2.34 (t, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 2H); 2.23 (s, 3H); 1.73 – 1.66 (m, 2H); 1.65 – 1.59 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 175.67, 157.40, 152.43, 147.15, 140.29, 136.02, 130.27, 124.72, 124.52, 124.24, 120.16, 119.62, 116.17, 115.39, 112.21, 27.58, 22.35, 22.18, 21.98, 21.41 ppm.

1.1.2.15. 7-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-32)

Yield: 26%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.44 (bs, 1H); 7.54 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.51 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H); 7.37 (dd, *J* = 8.9; 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.29 (t, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 1H); 6.76 – 6.72 (m, 1H); 6.61 (t, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H); 6.58 – 6.54 (m, 1H); 3.74 (s, 3H); 2.73 – 2.65 (m, 2H); 2.46 – 2.38 (m, 2H); 1.80 – 1.65 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 175.67; 161.22; 158.62; 152.10; 147.18; 136.14; 131.03; 124.52; 124.28; 120.16; 115.42; 112.48; 110.95; 109.61; 105.15; 55.74; 27.59; 22.34; 22.18; 21.98 ppm.

1.1.2.16. 7-(4-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-33)

Yield: 43%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.40 (bs, 1H); 7.52 – 7.49 (m, 1H); 7.42 – 7.40 (m, 1H); 7.36 – 7.33 (m, 1H); 7.22 – 7.18 (m, 2H); 6.95 – 6.91 (m, 2H); 2.68 (t, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 2H); 2.40 (t, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 2H); 2.29 (s, 3H); 1.76 – 1.64 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 175.36, 154.54, 152.73, 146.75, 135.51, 132.96, 130.64, 124.19, 123.55, 119.80, 119.13, 115.02, 111.07, 27.28, 22.05, 21.89, 21.68, 20.45 ppm.

1.1.2.17. 7-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-34)

Yield: 66%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. Given its limited solubility, compound **II-34** was used directly for the next step without additional analysis.

1.1.2.18. 7-(4-chlorophenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-35)

Yield: 82%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.44 (bs, 1H); 7.54 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.50 (d, *J* = 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.43 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H); 7.38 (dd, *J* = 9.0; 3.0 Hz, 1H); 7.04 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H); 2.73 – 2.64 (m, 2H); 2.44 – 2.36 (m, 2H); 1.77 – 1.67 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 175.32, 156.13, 151.55, 146.95, 136.01, 130.09, 127.38, 124.22, 123.96, 120.36, 120.04, 115.21, 112.35, 27.28, 22.02, 21.86, 21.66 ppm.

1.1.2.19. 7-(4-*tert*-butylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-36)

Yield: 66%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.43 (bs, 1H); 7.55 – 7.51 (m, 1H); 7.45 – 7.44 (m, 1H); 7.43 – 7.39 (m, 2H); 7.38 – 7.35 (m, 1H); 6.98 – 6.94 (m, 2H); 2.70 (t, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 2H); 2.41 (t, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 2H); 1.79 – 1.72 (m, 2H); 1.72 – 1.65 (m, 2H); 1.29 (s, 9H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 175.67; 154.8; 152.81; 147.12; 146.41; 135.8; 127.24; 124.49; 124.04; 120.13; 118.86; 115.35; 111.62; 34.54; 31.73; 27.58; 22.34; 22.18; 21.97 ppm.

1.1.2.20. 7-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydroacridin-9-one (II-38)

Yield: 91%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.42 (bs, 1H); 7.55 – 7.49 (m, 1H); 7.48 – 7.42 (m, 1H); 7.37 – 7.32 (m, 1H); 6.83 – 6.75 (m, 1H); 6.66 – 6.59

(m, 2H); 2.73 – 2.66 (m, 2H); 2.44 – 2.37 (m, 2H); 2.25 (s, 6H); 1.80 – 1.64 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 175.68; 157.44; 152.50; 147.14; 139.89; 135.98; 125.54; 124.52; 124.29; 120.12; 116.73; 115.37; 112.27; 108.39; 27.58; 22.35; 22.18; 21.98; 21.35 ppm.

1.1.2.21. 2-phenoxy-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-28)

Yield: 74%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. Given its limited solubility, compound III-28 was used directly for the next step without additional analysis.

1.1.2.22. 2-(2-methylphenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-29)

Yield: 57%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.42 (bs, 1H); 7.47 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H); 7.31 – 7.26 (m, 2H); 7.21 (d, *J* = 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.19 – 7.15 (m, 1H); 7.10 – 7.05 (m, 1H); 6.89 – 6.85 (m, 1H); 2.77 – 2.72 (m, 2H); 2.69 – 2.63 (m, 2H); 2.10 (s, 3H); 1.74 – 1.67 (m, 2H); 1.61 – 1.55 (m, 2H); 1.39 – 1.32 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 174.41; 154.42; 153.65; 153.13; 134.98; 132.11; 129.79; 128.05; 124.90; 124.84; 122.93; 120.51; 120.32; 110.31; 34.00; 32.30; 27.66; 26.29; 23.53; 16.27 ppm.

1.1.2.23. 2-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-30)

Yield: 40%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.44 (bs, 1H); 7.53 – 7.48 (m, 1H); 7.35 – 7.31 (m, 1H); 7.27 – 7.18 (m, 3H); 7.10 – 7.07 (m, 1H); 7.04 – 6.98 (m, 1H); 3.73 (s, 3H); 2.84 – 2.78 (m, 2H); 2.78 – 2.69 (m, 2H); 1.80 – 1.78 (m, 2H); 1.71 – 1.62 (m, 2H); 1.45 – 1.41 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 174.44; 154.30; 153.00; 151.91; 144.10; 126.25; 124.74; 122.40; 122.30; 121.67; 120.17; 114.04; 109.15; 56.10; 34.00; 32.31; 27.69; 26.31; 23.53 ppm.

1.1.2.24. 2-(3-methylphenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-31)

Yield: 35%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.55 (bs, 1H); 7.60 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.53 (d, *J* = 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.42 (dd, *J* = 8.9; 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.33 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H); 7.05 – 7.01 (m, 1H); 6.91 – 6.85 (m, 2H); 2.90 – 2.85 (m, 2H); 2.83 – 2.78 (m, 2H); 2.34 (s, 3H); 1.87 – 1.81 (m, 2H); 1.74 – 1.68 (m, 2H); 1.52 – 1.45 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 174.49; 157.37; 153.27; 152.90; 140.30; 135.46; 130.28; 124.89; 124.75; 124.06; 120.51; 120.43; 119.66; 116.22; 112.74; 34.02; 32.30; 27.65; 26.28; 23.53; 21.40 ppm.

1.1.2.25. 2-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-32)

Yield: 40%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.52 (bs, 1H); 7.57 – 7.54 (m, 1H); 7.53 – 7.52 (m, 1H); 7.40 – 7.36 (m, 1H); 7.32 – 7.26 (m, 1H); 6.76 – 6.73 (m, 1H); 6.63 – 6.61 (m, 1H); 6.58 – 6.55 (m, 1H); 3.74 (s, 3H); 2.85 – 2.79 (m, 2H); 2.78 – 2.72 (m, 2H); 1.84 – 1.75 (m, 2H); 1.71 – 1.63 (m, 2H); 1.47 – 1.40 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 174.51; 161.23; 158.57; 153.32; 152.58; 135.57; 131.03; 124.88; 124.09; 120.51; 120.47; 112.97; 111.01; 109.65; 105.23; 55.75; 34.02; 32.30; 27.65; 26.27; 23.54 ppm.

1.1.2.26. 2-(4-methylphenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-33)

Yield: 74%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.47 (bs, 1H); 7.52 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.42 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H); 7.36 – 7.33 (m, 1H); 7.20 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H); 6.95 – 6.92 (m, 2H); 2.83 – 2.79 (m, 2H); 2.76 – 2.71 (m, 2H); 2.30 (s, 3H); 1.80 – 1.75 (m, 2H); 1.67 – 1.62 (m,

2H); 1.45 – 1.39 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 174.15, 154.50, 153.15, 152.86, 134.93, 132.97, 130.63, 124.53, 123.35, 120.12, 120.05, 119.14, 111.60, 33.70, 31.99, 27.35, 25.98, 23.22, 20.44 ppm.

1.1.2.27. 2-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-34)

Yield: 55%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.72 (bs, 1H); 7.60 – 7.53 (m, 1H); 7.42 – 7.33 (m, 2H); 7.07 – 6.94 (m, 4H); 3.77 (s, 3H); 2.91 – 2.81 (m, 2H); 2.78 – 2.70 (m, 2H); 1.84 – 1.73 (m, 2H); 1.71 – 1.60 (m, 2H); 1.51 – 1.36 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 173.65, 156.25, 154.59, 153.69, 149.93, 134.90, 124.52, 123.35, 121.32, 120.55, 120.40, 115.65, 110.60, 55.90, 34.00, 32.23, 27.62, 26.25, 23.60 ppm.

1.1.2.28. 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-35)

Yield: 29%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.51 (bs, 1H); 7.55 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.51 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H); 7.45 – 7.41 (m, 2H); 7.40 – 7.36 (m, 1H); 7.07 – 7.03 (m, 2H); 2.85 – 2.80 (m, 2H); 2.77 – 2.72 (m, 2H); 1.82 – 1.75 (m, 2H); 1.69 – 1.61 (m, 2H); 1.46 – 1.39 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 174.14, 156.10, 153.07, 151.99, 135.45, 130.19, 130.08, 127.40, 124.57, 123.79, 120.39, 120.24, 112.89, 33.71, 31.98, 27.32, 25.96, 23.22 ppm.

1.1.2.29. 2-(4-*tert*-butylphenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-36)

Yield: 48%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.40 (bs, 1H); 7.46 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H); 7.37 (d, *J* = 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.35 – 7.32 (m, 2H); 7.30 – 7.26 (m, 1H); 6.90 – 6.86 (m, 2H); 2.77 – 2.72 (m, 2H); 2.69 – 2.64 (m, 2H); 1.73 – 1.67 (m, 2H); 1.60 – 1.55 (m, 2H); 1.40 – 1.31 (m, 2H); 1.21 (s, 9H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 174.47; 154.82; 153.26; 153.22; 146.44; 135.32; 127.25; 124.86; 123.84; 120.48; 120.38; 118.90; 112.16; 34.55; 34.01; 32.30; 31.73; 27.66; 26.28; 23.53 ppm.

1.1.2.30. 2-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-5H,6H,7H,8H,9H,10H,11H-cyclohepta[b]quinolin-11-one (III-38)

Yield: 48%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 300.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 11.49 (bs, 1H); 7.54 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H); 7.46 (d, *J* = 2.9 Hz, 1H); 7.35 (dd, *J* = 8.9; 2.8 Hz, 1H); 6.80 (s, 1H); 6.66 – 6.60 (m, 2H); 2.86 – 2.80 (m, 2H); 2.78 – 2.72 (m, 2H); 2.25 (s, 6H); 1.84 – 1.75 (m, 2H); 1.72 – 1.62 (m, 2H); 1.49 – 1.39 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 174.49, 157.40, 153.26, 152.97, 139.90, 135.42, 125.58, 124.88, 124.09, 120.47, 120.41, 116.78, 112.77, 34.02, 32.31, 27.66, 26.29, 23.53, 21.35 ppm.

1.1.3. General procedure for the preparation of compounds I-III 39-49

The intermediates **I-III 28-38** (1.0 eq.) were charged into a 250 mL round-bottom flask and POCl₃ (7.8 eq.) was added slowly under constant cooling in ice-water. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux at 130 °C for 1 h. Residual POCl₃ was distilled off *in vacuo* and the distillation residue was diluted with 50 mL DCM, poured onto a mixture containing 150 mL ice and water and concentrated aqueous NH₃ (25 %, 30 mL), and shaken three times in a separation funnel with DCM (3 × 50 mL). The organic phases were combined, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under

reduced pressure, and the crude reaction mixture containing compounds I-III 39-49 was purified by flash chromatography using PE/EA (4:1) mobile phase.

1.1.3.1. 9-chloro-7-phenoxy-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline (I-39)

Yield: 74%. Yellow viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.00 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H); 7.66 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.44 – 7.36 (m, 3H); 7.19 – 7.15 (m, 1H); 7.11 – 7.07 (m, 2H); 3.22 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 3.15 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H); 2.29 – 2.19 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 166.29; 156.87; 155.53; 145.39; 136.58; 134.54; 130.82; 129.96; 126.37; 123.85; 122.56; 119.14; 110.23; 35.34; 30.58; 22.77 ppm.

1.1.3.2. 9-chloro-7-(2-methylphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline (I-40)

Yield: 55%. Yellow viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.92 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H); 7.40 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H); 7.32 – 7.27 (m, 1H); 7.26 – 7.20 (m, 1H); 7.17 – 7.11 (m, 1H); 7.09 – 7.02 (m, 1H); 6.92 – 6.88 (m, 1H); 3.14 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 3.06 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H); 2.19 (s, 3H); 2.18 – 2.12 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 162.98, 156.47, 154.02, 142.66, 138.82, 134.38, 131.71, 130.68, 130.11, 127.38, 126.55, 124.61, 121.70, 120.05, 109.03, 39.93, 31.83, 30.47, 27.44, 26.93, 16.22 ppm.

1.1.3.3. 9-chloro-7-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline (I-41)

Yield: 74%. Yellow viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.91 – 7.87 (m, 1H); 7.48 – 7.44 (m, 1H); 7.34 – 7.28 (m, 1H); 7.15 – 7.10 (m, 1H); 7.02 – 6.96 (m, 2H); 6.92 – 6.88 (m, 1H); 3.75 (s, 3H); 3.12 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 3.05 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H); 2.15 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 165.71; 156.36; 151.51; 144.93; 144.45; 136.55; 134.40; 130.43; 126.31; 125.50; 121.51; 121.32; 121.29; 113.01; 108.13; 55.94; 35.28; 30.49; 22.73 ppm.

1.1.3.4. 9-chloro-7-(3-methylphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline (I-42)

Yield: 39%. Yellow viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.92 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H); 7.57 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.32 (dd, *J* = 9.1; 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.21 – 7.13 (m, 1H); 6.91 – 6.87 (m, 1H); 6.83 – 6.77 (m, 2H); 3.14 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 3.06 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H); 2.27 (s, 3H); 2.16 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 166.10, 156.75, 155.74, 145.05, 140.19, 136.75, 134.57, 130.56, 129.64, 126.38, 124.66, 122.67, 119.82, 116.14, 110.28, 35.25, 30.48, 22.72, 21.41 ppm.

1.1.3.5. 9-chloro-7-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline (I-43)

Yield: 75%. Yellow viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.97 – 7.92 (m, 1H); 7.62 – 7.59 (m, 1H); 7.37 – 7.32 (m, 1H); 7.23 – 7.17 (m, 1H); 6.66 – 6.62 (m, 1H); 6.59 – 6.55 (m, 2H); 3.72 (s, 3H); 3.15 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 3.08 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H); 2.17 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 166.24; 161.10; 158.01; 155.38; 145.16; 136.80; 134.62; 130.64; 130.35; 126.39; 122.75; 111.19; 110.61; 109.54; 105.13; 55.42; 35.30; 30.50; 22.73 ppm.

1.1.3.6. 9-chloro-7-(4-methylphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline (I-44)

Yield: 32%. Yellow viscous oil. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.97 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H); 7.46 (dd, *J* = 9.1; 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.37 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.27 – 7.23 (m, 2H); 7.06 – 7.02 (m, 2H); 3.09 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 3.04 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H); 2.32 (s, 3H); 2.18 – 2.08 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 166.27; 156.15; 153.59; 144.74; 134.97; 134.62; 133.85; 131.19; 130.82; 125.56; 122.17; 119.71; 107.94; 34.73; 30.18; 22.44; 20.50 ppm.

1.1.3.7. 9-chloro-7-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline (I-45)

Yield: 69%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.92 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.46 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.32 (dd, $J = 9.1; 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.00 – 6.95 (m, 2H); 6.89 – 6.84 (m, 2H); 3.76 (s, 3H); 3.15 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H); 3.06 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H); 2.16 (p, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 165.68, 156.99, 156.32, 149.60, 144.61, 136.75, 134.56, 130.43, 126.35, 121.96, 121.07, 115.07, 108.46, 55.67, 35.21, 30.49, 22.73 ppm.

1.1.3.8. 9-chloro-7-(4-chlorophenoxy)-1H,2H,3H-cyclopenta[b]quinoline (I-46)

Yield: 56%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 8.03 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, 1H); 7.54 – 7.48 (m, 4H); 7.19 – 7.15 (m, 2H); 3.15 – 3.08 (m, 4H); 2.22 – 2.12 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 166.81, 155.14, 145.09, 135.10, 134.90, 131.44, 130.32, 129.89, 128.23, 125.56, 122.53, 121.19, 109.25, 34.78, 30.15, 22.40 ppm.

1.1.3.9. 9-chloro-7-(4-tert-butylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H-cyclopenta[b]quinoline (I-47)

Yield: 34%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.94 – 7.90 (m, 1H); 7.61 – 7.58 (m, 1H); 7.35 – 7.28 (m, 3H); 6.95 – 6.91 (m, 2H); 3.15 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H); 3.08 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H); 2.21 – 2.12 (m, 2H); 1.27 (s, 9H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 166.04; 155.85; 154.33; 146.74; 145.08; 136.69; 134.53; 130.57; 126.77; 126.40; 122.51; 118.60; 110.16; 35.30; 34.40; 31.50; 30.50; 22.73 ppm.

1.1.3.10. 9-chloro-7-(4-acetylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H-cyclopenta[b]quinoline (I-48)

Yield: 45%. Yellow viscous oil. The product (compound I-48) was used directly in the next reaction step without further analysis.

1.1.3.11. 9-chloro-7-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-1H,2H,3H-cyclopenta[b]quinoline (I-49)

Yield: 63%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.95 – 7.90 (m, 1H); 7.60 – 7.57 (m, 1H); 7.34 – 7.30 (m, 1H); 6.73 – 6.71 (m, 1H); 6.63 – 6.59 (m, 2H); 3.15 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H); 3.07 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H); 2.23 (s, 6H); 2.17 (p, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 166.00; 156.78; 155.80; 144.99; 139.82; 136.80; 134.54; 130.49; 126.41; 125.57; 122.77; 116.79; 110.38; 35.27; 30.50; 22.74; 21.34 ppm.

1.1.3.12. 9-chloro-7-(2-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-40)

Yield: 86%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.89 – 7.85 (m, 1H); 7.39 – 7.36 (m, 1H); 7.31 – 7.26 (m, 1H); 7.24 – 7.20 (m, 1H); 7.16 – 7.11 (m, 1H); 7.07 – 7.03 (m, 1H); 6.92 – 6.88 (m, 1H); 3.02 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 2.90 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H); 2.18 (s, 3H); 1.88 – 1.83 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.63; 156.21; 154.02; 143.17; 140.36; 131.71; 130.60; 130.09; 129.27; 127.37; 126.40; 124.60; 122.07; 120.04; 107.92; 33.92; 27.59; 22.71; 22.64; 16.22 ppm.

1.1.3.13. 9-chloro-7-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-41)

Yield: 86%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.87 – 7.84 (m, 1H); 7.45 – 7.42 (m, 1H); 7.33 – 7.29 (m, 1H); 7.14 – 7.09 (m, 1H); 7.01 – 6.95 (m, 2H); 6.93 – 6.87 (m, 1H); 3.74 (s, 3H); 3.01 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 2.89 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H); 1.87 – 1.83 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.57; 156.32; 151.50; 144.43; 143.19; 140.42; 130.31; 129.18; 126.32; 125.49; 121.83; 121.50; 121.29; 113.01; 107.86; 55.94; 33.89; 27.58; 22.71; 22.64 ppm.

1.1.3.14. 9-chloro-7-(3-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-42)

Yield: 57%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.92 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.57 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.32 (dd, $J = 9.1; 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.21 – 7.13 (m, 1H); 6.91 – 6.87 (m, 1H); 6.83 – 6.77 (m, 2H); 3.14 (t, $J =$

7.7 Hz, 2H); 3.06 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H); 2.27 (s, 3H); 2.16 (p, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.91, 156.68, 155.78, 140.21, 130.34, 129.65, 129.37, 126.41, 124.70, 123.20, 119.86, 116.19, 114.84, 114.68, 110.03, 33.75, 27.57, 23.91, 22.62, 21.42 ppm.

1.1.3.15. 9-chloro-7-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-43)

Yield: 87%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.92 – 7.86 (m, 1H); 7.63 – 7.58 (m, 1H); 7.36 – 7.32 (m, 1H); 7.21 – 7.16 (m, 1H); 6.65 – 6.61 (m, 1H); 6.59 – 6.55 (m, 2H); 3.71 (s, 3H); 3.04 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H); 2.92 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 1.89 – 1.85 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 161.09; 158.14; 157.99; 155.32; 143.49; 140.60; 130.59; 130.34; 129.37; 126.36; 123.13; 111.21; 110.40; 109.55; 105.12; 55.42; 33.94; 27.59; 22.68; 22.61 ppm.

1.1.3.16. 9-chloro-7-(4-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-44)

Yield: 79%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.94 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.61 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.40 (dd, $J = 9.1$; 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.21 – 7.17 (m, 2H); 7.02 – 6.98 (m, 2H); 3.11 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 2.99 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H); 2.37 (s, 3H); 1.97 – 1.92 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.88; 156.17; 154.24; 144.46; 140.36; 133.55; 130.61; 130.47; 129.25; 126.34; 122.67; 119.33; 109.21; 34.00; 27.59; 22.78; 22.64; 20.73 ppm.

1.1.3.17. 9-chloro-7-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-45)

Yield: 85%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.98 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.54 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.41 (dd, $J = 9.1$; 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.09 – 7.05 (m, 2H); 6.97 – 6.94 (m, 2H); 3.85 (s, 3H); 3.13 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 3.00 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 2.00 – 1.91 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.58, 156.95, 156.31, 149.57, 142.92, 140.60, 130.34, 129.30, 126.34, 122.43, 121.08, 119.37, 115.07, 111.80, 108.19, 55.67, 33.79, 27.57, 22.65, 22.60 ppm.

1.1.3.18. 9-chloro-7-(4-chlorophenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-46)

Yield: 59%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.97 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.63 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.39 (dd, $J = 9.1$; 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.36 – 7.32 (m, 2H); 7.04 – 7.00 (m, 2H); 3.11 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H); 3.00 (t, $J = 6.3$ Hz, 2H); 1.97 – 1.93 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 158.36, 155.40, 155.14, 143.64, 140.40, 130.89, 129.92, 129.44, 128.86, 126.27, 122.74, 120.39, 110.15, 33.98, 27.55, 22.64, 22.56 ppm.

1.1.3.19. 9-chloro-7-(4-tert-butylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-47)

Yield: 49%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.90 – 7.85 (m, 1H); 7.59 – 7.57 (m, 1H); 7.34 – 7.28 (m, 3H); 6.94 – 6.90 (m, 2H); 3.03 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 2.91 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H); 1.91 – 1.82 (m, 4H); 1.26 (s, 9H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.91; 155.80; 154.30; 146.72; 143.37; 140.53; 130.50; 129.29; 126.76; 126.40; 122.94; 118.61; 109.93; 34.40; 33.93; 31.51; 27.59; 22.70; 22.63 ppm.

1.1.3.20. 9-chloro-7-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine (II-49)

Yield: 83%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.91 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.58 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.32 (dd, $J = 9.1$; 2.7 Hz, 1H); 6.72 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 1H); 6.63 – 6.60 (m, 2H); 3.05 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 2.93 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 2.23 (s, 6H); 1.91 – 1.84 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.86; 156.74; 155.80; 139.81; 130.34; 129.32; 126.41; 125.58; 123.25; 116.81; 110.14; 33.82; 27.58; 22.66; 22.61; 21.34 ppm.

1.1.3.21. 11-chloro-2-phenoxy-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-39)

Yield: 81%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.97 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, 1H); 7.68 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.43 – 7.37 (m, 3H); 7.20 – 7.15 (m, 1H); 7.12 – 7.07 (m, 2H); 3.25 – 3.19 (m, 5H); 1.94 – 1.86 (m, 3H); 1.86 – 1.78 (m, 2H); 1.78 – 1.71 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 163.44, 156.80, 155.71, 143.23, 138.70, 134.34, 130.86, 129.91, 126.46, 123.77, 122.57, 119.14, 111.16, 40.09, 31.79, 30.43, 27.42, 26.89 ppm.

1.1.3.22. 11-chloro-2-(2-methylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (compound III-40)

Yield: 75%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.89 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.41 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.30 – 7.26 (m, 1H); 7.24 – 7.21 (m, 1H); 7.16 – 7.11 (m, 1H); 7.08 – 7.03 (m, 1H); 6.92 – 6.89 (m, 1H); 3.17 – 3.13 (m, 2H); 3.13 – 3.08 (m, 2H); 2.19 (s, 3H); 1.84 – 1.78 (m, 2H); 1.75 – 1.69 (m, 2H); 1.69 – 1.63 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 165.70, 156.30, 154.01, 144.70, 136.65, 134.55, 131.72, 130.57, 130.09, 127.38, 126.42, 124.62, 121.66, 120.03, 108.19, 35.24, 30.49, 22.74, 16.21 ppm.

1.1.3.23. 11-chloro-2-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-41)

Yield: 77%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.81 – 7.76 (m, 1H); 7.41 – 7.39 (m, 1H); 7.26 – 7.21 (m, 1H); 7.07 – 7.02 (m, 1H); 6.95 – 6.90 (m, 2H); 6.86 – 6.80 (m, 1H); 3.68 (s, 3H); 3.09 – 3.01 (m, 4H); 1.78 – 1.70 (m, 2H); 1.67 – 1.62 (m, 2H); 1.60 – 1.56 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 162.98; 156.52; 151.52; 144.48; 142.87; 138.76; 134.26; 130.53; 126.45; 125.48; 121.50; 121.41; 121.29; 113.01; 109.00; 55.96; 40.03; 31.84; 30.46; 27.46; 26.95 ppm.

1.1.3.24. 11-chloro-2-(3-methylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-42)

Yield: 95%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.92 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.59 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.33 (dd, $J = 9.1$; 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.22 – 7.15 (m, 1H); 6.90 (d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 1H); 6.83 – 6.78 (m, 2H); 3.20 – 3.15 (m, 2H); 3.14 – 3.10 (m, 2H); 2.28 (s, 3H); 1.86 – 1.80 (m, 2H); 1.78 – 1.71 (m, 2H); 1.70 – 1.62 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 163.29, 156.75, 155.98, 140.20, 134.45, 130.58, 129.65, 126.55, 124.67, 122.83, 119.84, 116.17, 111.16, 39.88, 31.82, 30.47, 27.43, 26.91, 21.42 ppm.

1.1.3.25. 11-chloro-2-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-43)

Yield: 98%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.93 – 7.87 (m, 1H); 7.63 – 7.61 (m, 1H); 7.35 – 7.31 (m, 1H); 7.20 – 7.15 (m, 1H); 6.65 – 6.61 (m, 1H); 6.59 – 6.55 (m, 2H); 3.71 (s, 3H); 3.17 – 3.11 (m, 4H); 1.85 – 1.79 (m, 2H); 1.75 – 1.70 (m, 2H); 1.69 – 1.64 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 163.53; 161.09; 158.06; 155.50; 143.22; 138.88; 134.43; 130.80; 130.34; 126.51; 122.77; 111.53; 111.18; 109.52; 105.09; 55.42; 40.05; 31.83; 30.47; 27.45; 26.92 ppm.

1.1.3.26. 11-chloro-2-(4-methylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-44)

Yield: 95%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.95 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, 1H); 7.64 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.40 (dd, $J = 9.1$; 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.19 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H); 7.02 – 6.97 (m, 2H); 3.25 – 3.18 (m, 4H); 2.38 (s, 3H); 1.92 – 1.88 (m, 2H); 1.84 – 1.78 (m, 2H); 1.75 – 1.73 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 163.22, 156.26, 154.27, 143.04, 138.66, 134.27, 133.47, 130.73, 130.40, 126.43, 122.30, 119.28, 110.40, 40.06, 31.80, 30.43, 27.43, 26.90, 20.75 ppm.

1.1.3.27. 11-chloro-2-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-45)

Yield: 79%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.89 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.47 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 1H); 7.31 (dd, $J = 9.1; 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.00 – 6.96 (m, 2H); 6.88 – 6.83 (m, 2H); 3.76 (s, 3H); 3.19 – 3.13 (m, 2H); 3.13 – 3.08 (m, 2H); 1.86 – 1.77 (m, 2H); 1.76 – 1.68 (m, 2H); 1.68 – 1.62 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 163.01, 157.14, 156.30, 149.65, 142.68, 138.89, 134.38, 130.58, 126.48, 122.02, 121.06, 115.06, 109.37, 55.67, 39.90, 31.82, 30.47, 27.44, 26.92 ppm.

1.1.3.28. 11-chloro-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-46)

Yield: 24%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 8.01 – 7.98 (m, 1H); 7.53 – 7.47 (m, 4H); 7.19 – 7.14 (m, 2H); 3.20 – 3.14 (m, 4H); 1.88 – 1.79 (m, 2H); 1.70 – 1.64 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 163.71, 155.38, 155.18, 142.96, 137.44, 134.60, 131.50, 130.31, 128.20, 125.69, 122.75, 121.14, 110.19, 31.19, 29.89, 27.18, 26.62 ppm.

1.1.3.29. 11-chloro-2-(4-tert-butylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-47)

Yield: 83%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.93 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.61 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 1H); 7.35 – 7.29 (m, 3H); 6.95 – 6.90 (m, 2H); 3.20 – 3.15 (m, 2H); 3.15 – 3.11 (m, 2H); 1.86 – 1.79 (m, 2H); 1.77 – 1.70 (m, 2H); 1.70 – 1.63 (m, 2H); 1.27 (s, 9H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 163.19, 156.12, 154.30, 146.75, 134.45, 130.44, 126.77, 126.58, 122.72, 118.61, 111.04, 34.40, 31.81, 31.50, 30.47, 27.42, 26.90, 23.90 ppm.

1.1.3.30. 11-chloro-2-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline (III-49)

Yield: 95%. Yellow viscous oil. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.95 (bs, 1H); 7.59 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.32 (dd, $J = 9.1; 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 6.72 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 1H); 6.64 – 6.59 (m, 2H); 3.24 – 3.16 (m, 2H); 3.16 – 3.11 (m, 2H); 2.23 (s, 6H); 1.87 – 1.80 (m, 2H); 1.77 – 1.70 (m, 2H); 1.70 – 1.63 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 163.11, 156.70, 139.84, 134.50, 126.59, 125.64, 123.05, 116.84, 111.18, 31.80, 30.47, 27.40, 26.89, 21.34 ppm.

1.1.4. General procedure for the preparation of compounds I-III 50-60

The intermediate compound **I-III 39-49** (1.0 eq.) was charged into a two-necked 100 mL flask and mixed with phenol (10.0 eq.) at 80 °C; the temperature was then increased to 180 °C. Gaseous NH_3 prepared *in situ* was bubbled through the reaction mixture. After completion of the amination reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and extracted between 2M NaOH (100 mL) and DCM (3 × 100 mL). The organic phases were combined, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure, and the product purified by flash chromatography using DCM/MeOH/25% aqueous NH_3 (9:1:0.1) as the mobile phase. Compounds **I-III 50-60** were obtained as free bases in yields of 7%-65%. For biological assays, compounds **I-III 50-60** were converted to their respective hydrochloride salts.

1.1.4.1. 7-phenoxy-1H,2H,3H-cyclopenta[b]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-50)

Yield: 50%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 157.2-158.1 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 14.66 (s, 1H); 8.71 (s, 1H); 8.24 – 8.12 (m, 1H); 8.00 – 7.95 (m, 1H); 7.56 – 7.52 (m, 1H); 7.40 – 7.36 (m, 2H); 7.16 – 7.12 (m, 1H); 7.03 – 7.00 (m, 2H); 3.16 – 3.12 (m, 2H); 2.83 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 2H); 2.20 – 2.13 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 166.61, 157.58, 153.21, 145.51, 143.80, 130.87, 129.78,

123.17, 121.99, 118.49, 118.22, 115.56, 107.83, 34.99, 27.40, 22.76 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₈H₁₇N₂O⁺ (m/z): 277.1336; found 277.1337.

1.1.4.2. 7-(2-methylphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-51)

Yield: 65%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 273.9 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.92 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H); 7.38 – 7.34 (m, 1H); 7.24 – 7.23 (m, 1H); 7.15 – 7.10 (m, 1H); 6.88 – 6.85 (m, 1H); 6.84 – 6.79 (m, 2H); 2.95 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H); 2.50 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H); 2.02 (s, 3H); 1.94 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 168.92; 156.85; 155.38; 153.80; 152.62; 146.28; 132.16; 131.10; 130.47; 128.08; 125.19; 123.80; 121.71; 120.40; 117.41; 34.44; 28.44; 23.25; 16.16 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₁₉N₂O⁺ (m/z): 291.1492; found 291.1491.

1.1.4.3. 7-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-52)

Yield: 21%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 185.6-186.2 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.84 – 7.81 (m, 1H); 7.77 – 7.73 (m, 1H); 7.22 – 7.19 (m, 3H); 7.04 – 6.94 (m, 2H); 3.76 (s, 3H); 3.00 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.83 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.12 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 162.64; 154.11; 151.40; 148.96; 144.92; 140.85; 126.72; 125.61; 121.58; 121.52; 120.98; 118.01; 114.47; 113.97; 109.08; 56.10; 33.60; 28.17; 22.64. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₁₉N₂O₂⁺ (m/z): 307.1442; found 307.1437 ppm.

1.1.4.4. 7-(3-methylphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-53)

Yield: 27%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 255.9 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.91 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.73 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H); 7.29 (dd, *J* = 9.1; 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.19 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H); 6.87 (dd, *J* = 7.5; 1.5 Hz, 1H); 6.76 – 6.70 (m, 2H); 2.94 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.21 (s, 3H); 2.05 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 163.41; 158.07; 152.48; 148.89; 140.19; 130.23; 127.40; 124.24; 123.65; 118.57; 118.11; 115.69; 115.15; 114.58; 112.16; 33.77; 28.15; 22.63; 21.45. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₁₉N₂O⁺ (m/z): 291.1492; found 291.1487 ppm.

1.1.4.5. 7-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-54)

Yield: 37%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 195.2-195.8 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.68 – 7.64 (m, 2H); 7.32 – 7.27 (m, 1H); 7.18 – 7.13 (m, 1H); 6.63 – 6.59 (m, 1H); 6.51 – 6.46 (m, 2H); 3.66 (s, 3H); 3.00 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.82 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H); 2.15 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 161.33; 158.64; 153.70; 149.70; 140.48; 130.10; 128.99; 125.34; 123.42; 119.06; 117.69; 114.63; 110.19; 108.76; 104.33; 54.45; 32.98; 27.24; 22.13. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₁₉N₂O₂⁺ (m/z): 307.1442; found 307.1434 ppm.

1.1.4.6. 7-(4-methylphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-55)

Yield: 9%. Black crystalline powder; melting point: 292.7 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.07 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 1H); 7.41 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.31 (dd, *J* = 9.2; 2.5 Hz, 1H); 7.14 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H); 6.90 – 6.87 (m, 2H); 5.65 (s, 2H); 3.21 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.85 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H); 2.34 (s, 3H); 2.21 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 162.82; 157.03; 154.56; 154.37; 147.41; 133.37; 130.36; 129.40; 126.85; 122.87; 119.51; 118.87; 117.57; 115.63; 108.04; 33.46; 29.66; 27.43; 22.48; 20.67 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₁₉N₂O⁺ (m/z): 291.1492; found 291.1512.

1.1.4.7. 7-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-56)

Yield: 34%. Black crystalline powder; melting point: 198.5-199.7 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 14.08 (bs, 1H); 8.07 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 8.01 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 1H); 7.54 (dd, *J* = 9.2; 2.5 Hz, 1H); 7.07 – 7.03 (m, 2H); 7.02 – 6.97 (m, 2H); 3.77 (s, 3H); 1.88 – 1.82 (m, 2H); 1.76 – 1.67 (m, 2H); 1.61 – 1.53 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 157.5; 156.3; 155.9; 154.0; 150.1; 133.3; 125.2; 122.2; 120.7; 117.3; 115.7; 114.8; 110.7; 55.9; 33.4; 31.3; 26.6; 25.8; 24.9 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₁₉N₂O₂⁺ (m/z): 307.1442; found 307.1438.

1.1.4.8. 7-(4-chlorophenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-57)

Yield: 36%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 281.5 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.86 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H), 7.72 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H), 7.42 – 7.38 (m, 2H), 7.27 – 7.23 (m, 1H), 7.01 – 6.97 (m, 2H), 6.38 (s, 2H), 2.89 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 2.80 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 2.10 – 2.00 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 166.20, 157.08, 150.85, 145.97, 145.89, 130.51, 129.93, 126.55, 121.65, 119.19, 118.31, 113.87, 111.54, 34.57, 27.79, 22.44 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₈H₁₆ClN₂O⁺ (m/z): 311.0946; found 311.0940.

1.1.4.9. 7-(4-*tert*-butylphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-58)

Yield: 15%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 150.2 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.62 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 1H); 7.55 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.29 – 7.24 (m, 2H); 7.16 (dd, *J* = 9.1; 2.6 Hz, 1H); 6.84 – 6.80 (m, 2H); 2.90 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.07 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H); 1.20 (s, 9H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 164.63; 155.41; 153.43; 147.50; 145.88; 143.34; 128.99; 127.54; 126.36; 122.10; 118.07; 117.62; 114.80; 114.29; 109.42; 33.76; 30.53; 27.15; 22.23 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₂H₂₅N₂O⁺ (m/z): 333.1962; found 333.1961.

1.1.4.10. 1-[4-((9-amino-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinolin-7-yl)oxy)phenyl]ethan-1-one hydrochloride (I-59)

Yield: 15%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 162.5-166.8 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.94 – 7.90 (m, 2H); 7.77 – 7.72 (m, 1H); 7.36 – 7.30 (m, 1H); 7.09 – 7.08 (m, 1H); 7.01 – 6.97 (m, 1H); 2.91 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.76 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H); 2.47 (s, 3H); 2.04 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 196.91, 162.36, 157.79, 150.78, 148.01, 132.02, 131.26, 129.82, 128.94, 123.48, 119.24, 118.32, 117.09, 115.69, 114.57, 113.07, 34.23, 28.13, 27.03, 22.66 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₀H₁₉N₂O₂⁺ (m/z): 319.1442; found 319.1441.

1.1.4.11. 7-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-1*H*,2*H*,3*H*-cyclopenta[*b*]quinoline-9-amine hydrochloride (I-60)

Yield: 12%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 141.2-142.5 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.66 – 7.61 (m, 2H); 7.28 – 7.24 (m, 1H); 6.70 – 6.67 (m, 1H); 6.55 – 6.50 (m, 2H); 3.00 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H); 2.80 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H); 2.19 – 2.10 (m, 8H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 162.00; 157.30; 154.27; 149.96; 139.72; 128.98; 124.92; 124.86; 123.45; 119.05; 117.62; 116.02; 114.80; 114.61; 109.83; 43.48; 32.82; 27.26; 22.10; 19.98 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₀H₂₁N₂O⁺ (m/z): 305.1649; found 305.1645.

1.1.4.12. 7-(2-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-51)

Yield: 7%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 205.8-206.3 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 6.85 – 6.78 (m, 1H); 6.70 – 6.65 (m, 1H); 6.42 – 6.38 (m, 2H); 6.33 – 6.26 (m, 1H); 6.23 – 6.16 (m, 1H); 6.01 –

5.97 (m, 1H); 2.02 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 1.69 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 1.37 (s, 3H); 1.08 – 0.96 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 153.87; 153.53; 153.47; 150.02; 138.48; 130.48; 128.55; 126.28; 124.91; 123.12; 121.59; 118.05; 116.33; 108.62; 106.57; 30.15; 22.18; 21.27; 21.06; 14.12 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}^+$ (m/z): 305.1649; found 305.1649.

1.1.4.13. 7-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-52)

Yield: 21%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 144.5-145.2 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 7.95 – 7.92 (m, 1H); 7.88 – 7.84 (m, 1H); 7.74 (bs, 1H); 7.35 – 7.31 (m, 1H); 7.24 – 7.17 (m, 2H); 7.08 – 7.03 (m, 1H); 7.01 – 6.96 (m, 1H); 3.74 (s, 3H); 2.93 (t, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H); 2.54 (t, $J = 5.8$ Hz, 2H); 1.87 – 1.78 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 154.76; 153.06; 152.38; 151.47; 144.41; 136.20; 125.98; 123.89; 123.14; 121.63; 121.35; 116.81; 114.04; 109.33; 108.76; 56.11; 29.68; 23.43; 21.95; 21.59 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^+$ (m/z): 321.1598; found 321.1591.

1.1.4.14. 7-(3-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-53)

Yield: 21%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 144.5-145.2 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 7.95 – 7.92 (m, 1H); 7.88 – 7.84 (m, 1H); 7.74 (bs, 1H); 7.35 – 7.31 (m, 1H); 7.24 – 7.17 (m, 2H); 7.08 – 7.03 (m, 1H); 7.01 – 6.96 (m, 1H); 3.74 (s, 3H); 2.93 (t, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H); 2.54 (t, $J = 5.8$ Hz, 2H); 1.87 – 1.78 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 158.47, 156.52, 151.56, 148.88, 143.03, 140.05, 130.13, 129.61, 123.87, 122.95, 118.25, 117.87, 114.85, 111.77, 109.65, 33.32, 24.05, 22.90, 22.85, 21.46 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^+$ (m/z): 321.1598; found 321.1591.

1.1.4.15. 7-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-54)

Yield: 39%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 152.7-153.6 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 8.05 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 1H); 7.82 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H); 7.41 – 7.37 (m, 1H); 7.27 (t, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 1H); 7.21 – 7.14 (m, 2H); 6.73 – 6.68 (m, 1H); 6.59 (t, $J = 2.4$ Hz, 1H); 6.55 – 6.51 (m, 1H); 3.73 (s, 3H); 2.89 (t, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H); 2.55 (t, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H); 1.87 – 1.78 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 161.19, 159.20, 154.69, 152.18, 151.12, 139.97, 130.99, 126.90, 124.24, 117.31, 112.00, 110.03, 109.60, 109.20, 104.21, 55.74, 31.49, 23.72, 22.37, 22.22 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^+$ (m/z): 321.1598; found 321.1593.

1.1.4.16. 7-(4-methylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-55)

Yield: 13%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 268.5 °C (decomposition). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 7.86 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 1H); 7.67 – 7.64 (m, 1H); 7.19 (s, 1H); 7.16 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H); 6.89 – 6.85 (m, 2H); 6.34 (s, 2H); 2.82 (t, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H); 2.54 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 2.27 (s, 3H); 1.83 – 1.78 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 156.43, 155.80, 151.61, 148.07, 143.17, 131.84, 130.43, 129.75, 122.01, 117.64, 117.62, 110.78, 109.32, 33.36, 23.82, 22.73, 22.65, 20.38 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}^+$ (m/z): 305.1649; found 305.1643.

1.1.4.17. 7-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-56)

Yield: 28%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 164.7-165.6 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 7.80 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 7.64 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, 1H); 7.17 (dd, $J = 9.0; 2.7$ Hz, 1H); 6.98 – 6.92 (m, 4H); 6.26 (bs, 2H); 3.74 (s, 3H); 2.81 (t, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H); 2.54 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H); 1.86 – 1.76 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 156.75, 155.52, 152.75, 151.49, 148.09, 143.58, 130.27, 121.65, 119.70, 118.00,

115.47, 110.08, 109.61, 55.87, 33.83, 24.16, 23.11, 23.00 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₀H₂₁N₂O₂⁺ (m/z): 321.1598; found 321.1592.

1.1.4.18. 7-(4-chlorophenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-57)

Yield: 58%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 296.5 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.90 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.69 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H); 7.42 – 7.37 (m, 2H); 7.27 – 7.23 (m, 1H); 7.01 – 6.97 (m, 2H); 6.35 (s, 2H); 2.82 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H); 2.54 (t, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 2H); 1.86 – 1.75 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 157.05, 156.85, 150.82, 148.07, 143.62, 130.16, 129.92, 126.57, 122.13, 119.19, 117.64, 111.30, 109.42, 33.47, 23.84, 22.75, 22.65 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₁₈ClN₂O⁺ (m/z): 325.1103; found 325.1097.

1.1.4.19. 7-(4-*tert*-butylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-58)

Yield: 36%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 132.3-133.8 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.64 – 7.60 (m, 2H); 7.32 – 7.29 (m, 2H); 7.28 – 7.24 (m, 1H); 6.88 – 6.84 (m, 2H); 2.83 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H); 2.50 (t, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 2H); 1.88 – 1.78 (m, 4H); 1.22 (s, 9H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 155.03; 154.08; 154.05; 151.45; 146.28; 138.89; 128.98; 126.49; 125.11; 123.62; 117.85; 117.00; 114.79; 109.41; 109.14; 33.80; 30.61; 30.51; 22.92; 21.99; 21.73 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₃H₂₇N₂O⁺ (m/z): 347.2118; found 347.2111.

1.1.4.20. 7-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridine-9-amine hydrochloride (II-60)

Yield: 40%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 155.2-156.4 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.91 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.69 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H); 7.23 (dd, *J* = 9.0; 2.6 Hz, 1H); 6.73 (s, 1H); 6.57 (s, 2H); 2.84 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H); 2.54 (t, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 2H); 2.22 (s, 5H); 1.86 – 1.77 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 158.52; 156.51; 151.63; 148.84; 143.03; 139.67; 129.60; 124.71; 123.00; 117.86; 115.43; 111.77; 109.63; 33.34; 24.05; 22.91; 22.86; 21.40 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₁H₂₃N₂O⁺ (m/z): 319.1805; found 319.1798.

1.1.4.21. 2-phenoxy-6*H*,7*H*,8*H*,9*H*,10*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-50)

Yield: 62%. White crystalline powder; melting point: 292.8 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.90 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.71 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H); 7.38 – 7.33 (m, 2H); 7.24 (dd, *J* = 9.0; 2.5 Hz, 1H); 7.11 – 7.06 (m, 1H); 6.99 – 6.96 (m, 2H); 6.39 (s, 2H); 3.01 – 2.95 (m, 2H); 2.83 – 2.76 (m, 2H); 1.83 – 1.76 (m, 2H); 1.66 – 1.60 (m, 2H); 1.59 – 1.52 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 163.47, 158.50, 151.85, 147.38, 143.23, 130.39, 130.29, 123.09, 122.40, 118.88, 117.73, 114.90, 112.28, 39.17, 32.05, 28.07, 27.10, 25.78 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₀H₂₁N₂O⁺ (m/z): 305.1649; found 305.1643.

1.1.4.22. 2-(2-methylphenoxy)-6*H*,7*H*,8*H*,9*H*,10*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-51)

Yield: 39%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 295.7 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.77 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H); 7.66 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H); 7.27 – 7.24 (m, 1H); 7.15 – 7.07 (m, 2H); 7.02 – 6.97 (m, 1H); 6.75 – 6.71 (m, 1H); 2.96 – 2.91 (m, 2H); 2.77 – 2.71 (m, 2H); 2.20 (s, 3H); 1.77 – 1.71 (m, 2H); 1.63 – 1.54 (m, 2H); 1.53 – 1.45 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 162.18, 155.65, 153.24, 131.91, 129.82, 128.69, 127.84, 123.90, 121.99, 119.24, 118.65, 118.26, 115.69, 114.86, 110.71, 38.17, 31.93, 27.83, 26.89, 25.63, 16.44 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₁H₂₃N₂O⁺ (m/z): 319.1805; found 319.1798.

1.1.4.23. 2-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-52)

Yield: 23%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 133.6 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.97 – 7.93 (m, 2H); 7.38 – 7.34 (m, 1H); 7.26 – 7.19 (m, 2H); 7.09 – 7.06 (m, 1H); 7.02 – 6.97 (m, 1H); 3.75 (s, 3H); 3.18 – 3.10 (m, 2H); 2.90 – 2.83 (m, 2H); 1.87 – 1.80 (m, 2H); 1.73 – 1.67 (m, 2H); 1.60 – 1.52 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 158.24; 155.55; 152.83; 151.52; 144.14; 129.80; 126.19; 123.14; 121.67; 121.56; 119.21; 117.49; 115.70; 114.68; 114.07; 109.17; 56.13; 34.22; 31.47; 26.88; 26.05; 25.04 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₁H₂₃N₂O₂⁺ (m/z): 335.1755; found 335.1745.

1.1.4.24. 2-(3-methylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-53)

Yield: 47%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 304.6 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.71 – 7.62 (m, 1H); 7.61 – 7.56 (m, 1H); 7.26 – 7.19 (m, 1H); 7.17 – 7.07 (m, 1H); 6.87 – 6.81 (m, 1H); 6.78 – 6.66 (m, 2H); 3.04 – 2.92 (m, 2H); 2.81 – 2.68 (m, 2H); 2.21 (s, 3H); 1.87 – 1.76 (m, 2H); 1.70 – 1.53 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 161.92, 157.66, 153.90, 149.02, 140.22, 139.97, 129.31, 126.75, 123.78, 122.75, 118.71, 118.25, 115.11, 115.01, 109.90, 36.90, 31.57, 29.38, 27.10, 26.43, 25.23 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₁H₂₃N₂O⁺ (m/z): 319.1805; found 319.1801.

1.1.4.25. 2-(3-methoxyphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-54)

Yield: 23%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 127.2 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 8.11 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.97 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H); 7.74 (bs, 1H); 7.53 – 7.48 (m, 1H); 7.32 – 7.27 (m, 1H); 6.76 – 6.72 (m, 1H); 6.64 – 6.60 (m, 1H); 6.58 – 6.53 (m, 1H); 3.74 (s, 3H); 3.15 – 3.10 (m, 2H); 2.88 – 2.84 (m, 2H); 1.87 – 1.80 (m, 2H); 1.73 – 1.66 (m, 2H); 1.60 – 1.54 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 161.24; 159.52; 158.80; 153.48; 152.08; 131.09; 125.11; 124.74; 117.74; 114.90; 112.52; 110.32; 109.57; 104.54; 55.78; 49.06; 35.07; 31.56; 27.02; 26.20; 25.14 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₁H₂₃N₂O₂⁺ (m/z): 335.1755; found 335.1745.

1.1.4.26. 2-(4-methylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-55)

Yield: 28%. Grey crystalline powder; melting point: 310.7 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.83 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.67 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H); 7.19 (dd, *J* = 9.0; 2.5 Hz, 1H); 7.15 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H); 6.89 – 6.85 (m, 2H); 6.31 (s, 2H); 2.99 – 2.94 (m, 2H); 2.81 – 2.76 (m, 2H); 2.27 (s, 3H); 1.83 – 1.75 (m, 2H); 1.66 – 1.59 (m, 2H); 1.58 – 1.52 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 163.13, 155.81, 152.09, 146.84, 142.96, 131.85, 130.43, 130.07, 121.68, 118.59, 117.66, 114.56, 111.31, 31.77, 27.82, 26.85, 25.51, 20.38 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M+H]⁺: calculated for C₂₁H₂₃N₂O⁺ (m/z): 319.1805; found 319.1798.

1.1.4.27. 2-(4-methoxyphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-56)

Yield: 32%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 149.2 °C (decomposition). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.70 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H); 7.58 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H); 7.09 (dd, *J* = 9.0; 2.6 Hz, 1H); 6.92 – 6.84 (m,

4H); 6.18 (s, 2H); 3.67 (s, 3H); 2.92 – 2.86 (m, 2H); 2.74 – 2.68 (m, 2H); 1.76 – 1.69 (m, 2H); 1.58 – 1.52 (m, 2H); 1.52 – 1.46 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 163.42, 155.53, 153.24, 151.50, 146.90, 143.28, 130.52, 121.33, 119.75, 118.93, 115.47, 114.86, 110.63, 55.87, 32.10, 28.18, 27.19, 25.84 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M+H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^+$ (m/z): 335.1755; found 335.1743.

1.1.4.28. 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-57)

Yield: 51%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 298.5 °C (decomposition). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 7.79 (d, J = 9.1 Hz, 1H), 7.73 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1H), 7.36 – 7.34 (m, 2H), 7.17 – 7.14 (m, 1H), 7.03 – 6.99 (m, 2H), 6.81 – 6.75 (m, 2H), 3.10 – 3.05 (m, 2H), 2.89 – 2.81 (m, 2H), 1.96 – 1.87 (m, 2H), 1.81 – 1.73 (m, 2H), 1.73 – 1.64 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 163.38, 158.41, 157.87, 154.79, 130.94, 130.36, 129.38, 128.19, 124.22, 120.84, 120.44, 119.58, 116.48, 116.17, 111.65, 38.20, 32.93, 28.43, 27.77, 26.59 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M+H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}^+$ (m/z): 339.1259; found 339.1254.

1.1.4.29. 2-(4-tert-butylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-58)

Yield: 36%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 302.5 °C (decomposition). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 7.71 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1H); 7.67 (d, J = 9.2 Hz, 1H); 7.36 – 7.31 (m, 3H); 6.90 – 6.86 (m, 2H); 3.04 – 2.97 (m, 2H); 2.81 – 2.76 (m, 2H); 1.87 – 1.81 (m, 2H); 1.73 – 1.67 (m, 2H); 1.63 – 1.56 (m, 2H); 1.23 (s, 9H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 159.36, 155.13, 154.73, 151.86, 146.61, 129.45, 126.60, 124.08, 123.75, 118.04, 117.65, 114.81, 109.79, 35.17, 33.83, 31.32, 30.49, 26.56, 25.98, 24.91 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M+H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_2\text{O}^+$ (m/z): 347.2118; found 347.2115.

1.1.4.30. 2-(3,5-dimethylphenoxy)-6H,7H,8H,9H,10H-cyclohepta[b]quinoline-11-amine hydrochloride (III-60)

Yield: 57%. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 275.5 °C (decomposition). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 8.33 (bs, 2H); 8.19 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1H); 8.13 (dd, J = 9.2; 1.5 Hz, 1H); 7.57 (dd, J = 9.1; 2.4 Hz, 1H); 6.80 (s, 1H); 6.64 (s, 2H); 3.23 – 3.18 (m, 2H); 2.91 – 2.86 (m, 2H); 2.25 (s, 6H); 1.88 – 1.80 (m, 2H); 1.75 – 1.68 (m, 2H); 1.60 – 1.52 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 157.74, 157.40, 154.44, 154.03, 139.99, 133.78, 129.78, 126.22, 125.65, 122.32, 117.29, 116.16, 115.70, 114.84, 112.63, 33.14, 31.37, 26.60, 25.85, 24.88, 21.37 ppm. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M+H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}^+$ (m/z): 319.1805; found 319.1802.

1. In silico study

The 3D structure of compound II-52 was built and converted into pdbqt-format by software OpenBabel (v. 2.0.2). The NMDAR/GluN1/GluN2B receptor structure was acquired from the RCSB database (PDB ID 5EWJ): Crystal structure of ATDs of the GluN1 subunit and GluN2B subunit in complex with ifenprodil; resolution 2.77 Å [42]. The receptor was prepared for the docking by the function DockPrep using the software Chimera (v. 1.14) and MGLTools (v. 1.5.4.). The semi-flexible docking calculations were done by Vina (v. 1.1.2) with flexible ligands and the rigid receptor structure. The docking poses were improved by MD simulation. The best-scored docking pose was taken as the initial state for MD simulation. The force-

field parameters for ligands/compounds were assessed using Antechamber (v. 20.0) applying GAFF. MD simulations were carried out using Gromacs (v. 2018.1). The receptor-ligand complex was simulated in the periodic water box using the TIP3P model. The system was neutralized by addition of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions at the concentration of 10 nM. The system energy was minimized and equilibrated in a 100 ps isothermal-isochoric (NVT) phase and then in a 100 ps isothermal-isobaric (NPT) phase. Afterwards, a 50 ns MD simulation was run at a temperature of 300 K. The molecular docking and MD simulation results were 3D visualized using PyMOL Molecular Graphics System (Version 2.4.1, Schrödinger, LLC). The two-dimensional/2D figure was generated with Maestro 12.3 (Schrödinger Release, Schrödinger, LLC, New York, NY, 2020).

2. Molecular biology, cell cultures, and transfection

In this study, we used DNA expression vectors encoding human versions of GluN1-1a (hGluN1), GluN2A (hGluN2A), and GluN2B (hGluN2B) subunits, as well as green fluorescent protein (GFP) to identify transfected cells. Human versions of GluN subunits carrying point mutations in the ifenprodil-binding site (hGluN1-Y109C, hGluN1-F113A, hGluN2B-I111F, hGluN2B-F114A, and hGluN2B-Q110F) or with a deletion of ATD in the GluN1-1a subunit (hGluN1- Δ ATD, missing amino acids 32-386) were prepared using the QuikChange site-directed mutagenesis kit (Agilent Technologies) and their accuracy was verified by DNA sequencing (Eurofins Genomics, Ebersberg, Germany). Human embryonic kidney 293 (HEK293) cells were cultured in Opti-MEM I medium containing 5% fetal bovine serum (FBS; all from Thermo Fisher Scientific) and transfected in Opti-MEM I medium containing a mixture of 0.9 mL of MATra-A reagent (IBA Lifesciences) and 600 ng of DNA vectors carrying genes encoding GFP, hGluN1, and hGluN2 subunits (200 ng each). We then placed the HEK293 cells on a magnetic plate for 20 min and finally trypsinized and cultured them in Opti-MEM I supplemented with 1% FBS, 20 mM MgCl₂, and 3 mM kynurenic acid (for the reduction of excitotoxic damage to transfected cells) on 35 mm glass coverslips coated with poly-L-lysine. Electrophysiological recordings were performed at room temperature within 24-48 h after the end of transfection.

2.1. Electrophysiology

Similarly to our previous studies, we performed whole-cell electrophysiological recordings from transfected HEK293 cells using an Axopatch 200B amplifier (Molecular Devices), with 80% series resistance (<10 M Ω) and capacitance compensation. Voltage-clamp recordings were performed using a holding membrane potential of -60 mV or 40 mV. Liquid junction potential was not compensated. Currents were filtered at 2 kHz using an eight-pole Bessel low-pass filter, digitized at 5 kHz, and recorded using pClamp 10 software (Molecular Devices). Glass pipettes (with tip resistance between 3-6 M Ω) were fabricated using a horizontal micropipette puller model P-1000 (Sutter Instrument Co.), and filled with an intracellular recording solution containing (in mM): 125 gluconic acid, 15 CsCl, 5 BAPTA, 10 HEPES, 3 MgCl₂, 0.5 CaCl₂, and 2 ATP-Mg salts (pH adjusted to 7.2 with CsOH). The extracellular recording solution (ECS) contained (in mM): 160 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 10 HEPES, 10 glucose, 0.2 EDTA, and 0.7 CaCl₂ (pH adjusted to 7.3 with NaOH). For the ECS application, we used a microprocessor-controlled multi-barrel rapid perfusion system with a time constant for solution exchange around the measured

cell of ~20 ms. In all experiments, the ECS contained a saturating concentration of the co-agonist glycine (100 μ M), and we activated NMDARs by applying a saturating concentration of the agonist L-glutamate (1 mM). Stock solutions of the 7-PhO-THA derivatives (30 mM) were freshly prepared before each experiment by dissolving them in DMSO. The resulting DMSO concentration ($\leq 1\%$) was the same in all applied ECS within each experiment. All chemicals used for electrophysiology experiments were purchased from Merck. Dose-response curves for the effect of 7-PhO-THA derivatives on NMDARs were obtained using *Equation 1*: $I = 1/(1 + ([\text{compound}]/IC_{50})^h)$, where IC_{50} is the concentration of the compound that will produce 50% inhibition of the agonist-induced current, $[\text{compound}]$ is the concentration of the compound, and h is the apparent Hill coefficient.

3. *In Vitro* Anti-Cholinesterase Assay

The inhibitory activity of 7-PhO-THA derivatives and all the reference compounds against human recombinant AChE (hAChE, E.C. 3.1.1.7, purchased from Merck) and human plasmatic butyrylcholinesterase (hBChE, E.C. 3.1.1.8, purchased from Merck) were determined using the modified Ellman's method, according to the previously published protocol [43]. The results are expressed as IC_{50} values (the concentration of the compound that is required to reduce cholinesterase activity by 50%). For the calculation of the degree of inhibition (I), the following *Equation 2* was used:

Equation 2

$$I = \left(1 - \frac{\Delta A_i}{\Delta A_0} \right) \times 100 \quad [\%]$$

where ΔA_i indicates the change in absorbance observed for adequate cholinesterase exposed to its corresponding inhibitor, and ΔA_0 indicates the change in absorbance when a phosphate buffer solution (PBS) was added instead of an inhibitor. Microsoft Excel 10 software (Microsoft Corporation, Redmont, USA) and Prism v. 5.02 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, USA) were used for statistical evaluation of the obtained data.

4. Cell viability assessment

Standard MTT assay (Merck) was used according to the manufacturer's protocol on the CHO-K1 cell line (Chinese hamster ovary, ECACC, Salisbury, UK) in order to compare the cytotoxic effect of the studied compounds [44]. The CHO-K1 cells were cultured according to ECACC recommended conditions and seeded in a density of 8,000 cells per well. Briefly, the tested compounds were dissolved in DMSO and subsequently diluted in growth medium (F-12) supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% penicillin/streptomycin so that the final concentration of DMSO did not exceed 0.5% (v/v). The CHO-K1 cells were exposed to the tested compounds for 24 h. The medium was then replaced with medium containing 10 μ M of MTT and the cells were allowed to produce formazan for another approximately 3 h under surveillance. Thereafter, the medium with MTT was removed and the crystals of formazan were dissolved in DMSO (100 μ L). Cell viability was assessed spectrophotometrically by the amount of formazan produced. Absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 570 nm with a reference wavelength

of 650 nm on Synergy HT (BioTek, Winooski, USA). The IC₅₀ values were then calculated from the control-subtracted triplicates using non-linear regression (four parameters) in GraphPad Prism 5 software (GraphPad Software, San Diego, USA). The final IC₅₀ values were obtained as a mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM) from three independent measurements.

5. *In vivo* pharmacokinetic study

5.1. *Animals*

Adult male Wistar rats (200-300 g) purchased from the Velaz breeding colony were used for the pharmacokinetic assessment of four promising compounds (**I-52**, **II-52**, **III-52**, **III-56**). The experiments were conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the European Union directive 2010/63/EU and Act No. 246/1992 Coll. The handling of the experimental animals was done under the supervision of the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Military Health Sciences, Czech Republic (approvals reference No. 15/21 and 19/21).

The rats were injected intraperitoneally (*i.p.*) with the tested compounds (5 mg/kg in 5% DMSO/5% kolliphor/saline (v/v) mixture). Blood samples were collected under deep terminal anesthesia directly by cardiac puncture into heparinized 1.5 mL tubes at 15 and 60 min (three animals per time interval). Four animals were used for zero time or blank control. The animals were perfused transcordially with a saline solution (0.9% NaCl) for 5 min (1 mL/min) and after the wash-out, the skull was opened and the brain carefully removed; brains were stored at -80 °C until homogenization.

The brains were weighed and four times the weight of PBS was added. The brains were subsequently homogenized by a T-25 Ultra Turrax disperser (IKA, Staufen, Germany), ultrasonicated by UP 50H needle homogenizer (Hielscher, Teltow, Germany), and stored at -80 °C prior to extraction.

5.2. *Sample extraction*

190 µL of brain homogenate or plasma were spiked with 10 µL of internal standard (IS) isotope-labeled donepezil-d₇ in methanol (IS, final concentration was 1 µM). The sample was alkalized with 100 µL of 1M sodium hydroxide and 0.7 mL of tert-butyl methyl ether was added. The samples were then shaken (1200 RPM, 10 min, Wizard Advanced IR Vortex Mixer, Velp Scientifica, Usmate, Italy) and centrifuged (12,000 RPM, 5 min, Universal 320 R centrifuge, Hettich, Tuttlingen, Germany). 500 µL of supernatant was transferred to a microtube and evaporated to dryness in a CentriVap concentrator (Labconco Corporation, Kansas City, USA). Calibration samples were prepared by the spiking of 180 µL of blank brain homogenate or plasma with 10 µL of the studied compound dissolved in methanol (final concentrations range from 0.5 nM to 50 µM) and with 10 µL of IS, final concentration of 1 µM). The calibration samples were then vortexed and extracted as above. The analyzed samples were reconstituted in 100 µL of acetonitrile/water mixture of 50/50 (v/v).

5.3. *Pharmacokinetic study - HPLC-MS analysis*

Compound levels in plasma and brain homogenate were measured by the above-mentioned UHPLC system with mass spectrometric detection. The results were obtained by the gradient elution method with a reverse phase on a RP Amide column (Ascentis Express, 2.1x100 mm, 2.7 µm, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Mobile phase A was ultrapure water of ASTM I type (resistance 18.2 MΩ.cm at 25°C)

prepared by Barnstead Smart2Pure 3 UV/UF apparatus (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) with 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid (LC-MS grade, Sigma Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany); mobile phase B was acetonitrile (MS grade, VWR International, Fontenay-sous-Bois, France) with 0.1 % (v/v) of formic acid. The gradient was as follows. Initially 10 % of mobile phase B flowed for 0.3 min; the gradient of mobile phase B then increased to 60 % during a period of 2.7 min, and then rose to 100 % in 0.7 min. After this 0.7 min of 100 % B flow, the composition returned to 10 % of B and was equilibrated for 3.5 min. The total run time of the gradient elution method was 7.5 min. The rate of flow of the mobile phase was set to 0.45 mL/min and the column was tempered to 40 °C. The injection volume was 5 µL. Samples were analyzed using the previously mentioned Orbitrap mass spectrometer in total ion current in positive mode. The calibration curves had 11 points and concentrations ranged from 0.5 nM to 50 µM; curves in both cases were linear within the measured range.

6. Acute toxicity evaluation-NOAEL

The acute toxicities of the compounds were assessed as no-observed-adverse-effect-level (NOAEL). Compounds were administered intraperitoneally (i.p., 5% DMSO with 5% Kolliphor in saline) in adult male Wistar rats. Rats were randomly assigned to the experimental groups consisting of four males per one administered dose of tested compounds. Selected doses were administered to identify NOEL and NOAEL with starting dose levels based on their solubility or according to our previous experience. All tested compounds were administered via i.p. injection in a standardized volume of 1 mL.kg⁻¹.

Treated rats were extensively observed for signs of toxicity in the first hour, and then periodically for two days. Clinical signs such as cardiovascular, respiratory, and nervous system disability, weight loss, or reduction of food consumption were observed according to Laboratory Animal Science Association (UK) guidelines. The severity of symptoms was classified as mild, moderate, and substantial [45]. During all acute toxicity studies, we followed the rules: i) if a category of substantial severity was achieved, the animal was immediately euthanized by CO₂, and a lower/more appropriate dose was selected to continue the study; ii) if a severe adverse effect or death occurred within a few minutes after administration to the first animal in the group, the other animal was not treated, and a lower dose was selected as well; iii) in the case of mortality or surviving 48 hours, all animals were euthanized by CO₂ and subjected to basic macroscopic necropsy [46].

7. Biotransformation experiments

7.1. Microsomal stability determination

The tested compounds I-52 and II-52 were incubated with Human Liver Microsomes according to the Cypotex assay protocol. Briefly, compounds were dissolved in DMSO (stock solution). 5 µL of stock solution was mixed with 12.5 µL of pooled Human Liver Microsomes (concentration 0.5 mg/mL, H2620, LOT no. 1210347, SekiSui, XenoTech, Canada) and 458 µL of 0.1M potassium phosphate buffer solution (pH = 7.4, adjusted by addition of NaOH) and preincubated for 5 min (300 RPM, 25°C). The final concentration of DMSO in the incubation mixture did not exceed 1% (v/v) and the concentration of tested compounds was set at 3 µM. The biotransformation reaction was started by addition of 25 µL of RapidStart NADPH Regenerating System (K5000, LOT. 1910008, SekiSui, XenoTech, Canada) and then incubated for 5 different time periods (0, 5, 15, 30, 45 min). The reaction was terminated by addition of

500 μL of cooled acetonitrile ($-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) with 1 μM internal standard (compound **2dC** from ref. [47]), and centrifuged for 5 min (14 000 RPM, 20°C). Subsequently, 400 μL of supernatant was transferred to the vial and analyzed by LC-MS.

7.2. HPLC-MS analysis

The LC-MS system used for the analysis of the samples was mentioned in the section “General methods and chemistry”. A reverse-phase C18 column Kinetex EVO (Phenomenex, Torrance, USA) was used as a stationary phase, and purified water with 0.1% formic acid (mobile phase A) and LC-MS grade acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid (mobile phase B) were used as the mobile phases. Gradient elution was set up to determine the mass spectra. The method started with 5% B for 0.3 min, the gradient then switched to 100% B in the third min, remained at 100% B for 0.7 min, and then reverted to 5% B with equilibration for 3.5 min. The total run time of the method was 7.5 min. The column temperature was kept constant at $27\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the flow of the mobile phase was 0.5 mL/min, and the injection volume was 1 μL .

7.3. Data evaluation

The peak areas of the compounds (Acmp) and internal standards (AIS) and formed metabolites were detected in extracted ion chromatograms from the mass spectrometer data in positive mode. The Acmp/AIS was calculated. From a plot of $\ln \text{Acmp}/\text{AIS}$ against time of incubation, the gradient (k value) was established. The $T_{1/2}$ value, and Cl_{int} were calculated according to the Cyprotex protocol and compared with the known fast and slow metabolically degraded standards of verapamil and diazepam (Table 3). The amount of 7-OH-TA metabolite was calculated after 45 min incubation as a ratio between the sum of the areas of all detected metabolites and the area of 7-OH-TA.

8. Behavioral experiments

8.1. Animals

Adult male Wistar rats (280–385 g, 2–3 months old) from the Velaz breeding colony, Czech Republic, were used. They were housed in pairs in standard plexiglass boxes ($42 \times 21 \times 20\text{ cm}$) in the animal facility of the National Institute of Mental Health, Czech Republic, with a 12:12 h light/dark cycle, with free access to food and water, and defined temperature and humidity. The experiments were performed during the light phase of the day, after a one week-long acclimatization period, and after habituation to handling by the experimenter. All experiments were performed in accordance with the guidelines of European Union directive 2010/63/EU and Act No. 246/1992 Coll. on the protection of animals against cruelty, and were approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee of the National Institute of Mental Health (reference number MZDR 9928/2023-5/OVZ).

8.2. Treatment

The compounds **I-52** and **II-52** were dissolved at concentrations of 2 and 5 mg/mL, respectively, and administered *i.p.* at a dose of 2 and 5 mg/kg of body weight respectively, 15 min before the beginning of the experiment. The compounds were dissolved in DMSO (5% of total vehicle volume; Dimethyl sulfoxide Rotipuran® p.a., Carl Roth, Germany) and added to a solution consisting of 5% Kolliphor EL (Glentham Life Sciences, UK) in physiological saline. Control animals received vehicle (VEH; 5% DMSO in 5% Kolliphor EL in saline) 15 min before the experiment. The (+)-MK-801 hydrogen maleate (MK-801, Merck) was dissolved in the same vehicle (0.2 and 0.3 mg/mL) and administered *i.p.* 30 min before the

experiment at a dose of 0.2 mg/kg of body weight (in the open-field test) and 0.3 mg/kg of body weight (in the pre-pulse inhibition test).

Scopolamine hydrobromide (Merck) was dissolved in saline (2 mg/mL) and administered *i.p.* at the dose of 2 mg/kg of body weight 20 min before the Morris water maze experiment. Control animals received saline.

In the open-field test and the pre-pulse inhibition of acoustic startle response test, each rat received one injection (compound **I-52**, compound **II-52**, MK-801 or vehicle), while in the Morris water maze test, each rat received two injections (co-administered with scopolamine; the treatment groups are described below).

8.3. The open-field test

The animals were pseudo-randomly ascribed to the following treatment groups: (1) VEH (vehicle; $n = 7$), (2) I-52 (compound **I-52**; $n = 6$), (3) II-52 (compound **II-52**; $n = 6$), (4) MK-801 ($n = 6$). The open-field apparatus consisted of a black plastic square arena (80 × 80 × 40 cm), located in a separate room with defined light conditions. The animal was placed in the center of the arena and recorded for 10 min by a camera fastened above the arena and connected to tracking software (EthoVision XT 16, Noldus, Netherlands). The arena was thoroughly cleaned between individual animals. The dependent variable was the distance moved by the animal.

8.4. The pre-pulse inhibition of acoustic startle response test

The treatment groups were as follows: (1) VEH (vehicle; $n = 7$), (2) I-52 (compound **I-52**; $n = 6$), (3) II-52 (compound **II-52**; $n = 6$), (4) MK-801 ($n = 6$). The pre-pulse inhibition of startle response is a physiological reduction of the amplitude of the motor startle response caused by presentation of a weak acoustic stimulus (pre-pulse) immediately before the startle-inducing acoustic stimulus (pulse). The dependent variable is the percent of the pre-pulse inhibition. The experimental setup is described in [12]; the only difference is the time interval between the drug administration and the testing session.

8.5. The Morris water maze test

The treatment groups were as follows: (1) VEH (received vehicle and saline; $n = 6$), (2) SCOP (received scopolamine hydrobromide and vehicle; $n = 6$), (3) I-52 + SCOP (received compound **I-52** and scopolamine hydrobromide; $n = 6$), (4) II-52 + SCOP (received compound **II-52** and scopolamine hydrobromide; $n = 5$). The Morris water maze consisted of a grey plastic pool (180 cm in diameter) filled with water (23 °C) colored by a small amount of non-toxic grey dye, with a hidden platform (circular, 10 cm in diameter, transparent plastic, submerged 1 cm below the water surface) placed in the same location throughout the experiment (in the center of the selected quadrant). The position of the rat was monitored by a camera fastened above the center of the pool connected to tracking software (EthoVision XT 16, Noldus, Netherlands).

The experiment was performed during four consecutive days. Each day the rats underwent eight training trials (swims; each 60 s long) from different starting positions located at the perimeter of the pool (labelled as N, S, E, W, NE, NW, SE, SW; each day in a different pseudo-random order). The rat was placed into the pool facing the inner wall and was allowed to search for the platform and then rest on it for 15 s. If the rat did not find the platform within the 60 s time limit, a latency of 60 s was recorded and

the rat was gently guided to the platform by the experimenter, allowed to rest on the platform for 15 s, and removed. The inter-trial interval was 6–7 min. After completing the training trials on day 4, an extra trial was conducted. The platform was removed from the pool and the rat was allowed to search for the platform for 60 s (probe trial).

During the training trials on days 1–4, the analyzed parameters were latency to find the platform and mean distance from the platform (mean of the distances of the animal from the platform, sampled in 40 ms intervals during the trial). Mean daily values per animal were used for analysis. In the probe trial, the number of platform area crossings was analyzed.

8.6. Statistics

The data were analyzed using Prism software v.8 (GraphPad, San Diego, USA). The differences were considered statistically significant at a level of $p < 0.05$. The data from the open-field and pre-pulse inhibition of acoustic startle response tests were analyzed using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Dunnett's multiple comparisons *post hoc* test (the comparison vs. VEH group). The latency and mean distance from the platform (daily means per animal) in the Morris water maze test were analyzed using two-way repeated measures ANOVA (two factors – the treatment and day) with the Geisser–Greenhouse correction. To investigate the effect of treatment, Tukey's *post hoc* test was conducted to compare overall mean latencies per group. The number of platform crossings in the probe trial was analyzed by Kruskal–Wallis test followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test.

9. NMDA-induced hippocampal lesions in rats

9.1. Animals

Experiments were conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the European Union directive 2010/63/EU and approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee which possesses the National Institutes of Health Statement of Compliance with Standards for Humane Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. Adult male Wistar rats (350–500 g) were used for experiments to assess the neuroprotective activity of compound **I-52**. The rats were kept in a controlled environment as described above in section 8.1 “Behavioral experiments”.

9.2. Drugs and experimental groups/Treatment

NMDA was dissolved in 10 mM sterile PBS to achieve a final concentration of 25 mM. Compound **I-52** was diluted in vehicle consisting of sterile 0.9% physiological saline solution containing 5% DMSO (Merck Millipore) and 5% Kolliphor EL to achieve a final concentration of 30 μ M. The solutions containing NMDA at 25 mM and compound **I-52** at 30 μ M were thoroughly mixed in a 1:1 ratio. The control group of animals received a mixed solution of NMDA (25 mM) and vehicle. The second control group received a mixed solution of 10 mM PBS and vehicle.

A total of $n = 28$ animals were used for the experiment ascribed to the following treatment groups: (1) NMDA + VEH (received NMDA and vehicle; $n = 10$), (2) PBS + VEH (received PBS and vehicle; $n = 9$), (3) NMDA + **I-52** (received NMDA and compound **I-52**; $n = 9$).

9.3. Surgery and histology

The animals underwent surgical preparation under 1.5-2.5% of isoflurane anesthesia (VetPharma). They were secured onto a stereotaxic apparatus (TSE systems, Berlin, Germany), with their eyes covered with a medical petroleum jelly (Vaseline, Unilever). They were carefully shaved, and the scalp was incised. A unilateral craniotomy was performed at the coordinates of -4 mm AP and 2.5 mm ML relative to the bregma, following the rat brain atlas of Paxinos and Watson (2014). Using a Hamilton 10 µL syringe, the right dorsal hippocampus was injected (DV = 4.6 mm). An infusion pump (model 540310 plus; TSE Systems, Berlin, Germany) maintained a constant flow rate of 0.25 µL/min for the application of the mixed solutions. The total volume administered to each animal was 2 µL. After surgery, the animals had free access to food and water containing analgesics.

At 24 h after the application of the mixed NMDA and compound **I-52** solutions, the rats were euthanized with an overdose of the anesthetics Narketan (ketamine; 100 mg/kg) and Rometar (xylazine; 20 mg/kg). Trans-cardial perfusion with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) diluted in 0.2 M phosphate buffer (PB) was performed. Brains were post-fixed 24 h in 4% PFA and gradually cryoprotected using increasing concentrations of sucrose solution (10, 20, and 30%; the brain was immersed in the solution until it sank to the bottom of the tube). Frozen cryoprotected brains were sliced in the coronal plane (50 µm, 1-in-5 series) from the beginning of the hippocampus (Bregma – 1.80 mm). All sections were collected and stored at -20 °C in cryoprotectant solution (ethylene glycol, glycerol, 0.2 M PB, distilled water - 3:3:1:3). Each series of slices underwent evaluation of the neurodegenerative damage of the afflicted hippocampus. The severity of hippocampal damage was determined in the following hippocampal regions: granular cell layer of the lower part of the dentate gyrus (DGL), granular cell layer of the higher part of the dentate gyrus (DGh), hilus, CA1, and CA3, as previously described in [48].

9.4 Statistics

The data (total scores of hippocampal damage) were analyzed by ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons *post hoc* test using Prism software v.8 (GraphPad, San Diego, USA). The differences were considered statistically significant at a level of $p < 0.05$.

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Conflict of interest:

Authors declare no competing interest.

Data Availability

Raw data will be provided upon request.

Supplementary data:

Supplementary data confirming the identity and purity of the novel compounds can be found online at xxx.

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